

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D2.2 MOBILISATION AND MUTUAL LEARNING REPORT 30/06/2025

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

Funded by the European Union Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Grant Agreement No.: 101094917
Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51
Type of action: CSA

D2.2 MOBILISATION AND MUTUAL LEARNING REPORT

Document information

Work package	WP Number
Task	T2.3 – Multi-level knowledge transfer among the implementers
Due date	30/06/2025
Submission date	26/06/2025
Deliverable lead	APRE
Version	1.0
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Authors	Stefania Laneve (APRE), Laura Mentini (APRE)
Editors	Stefania Laneve (APRE), Laura Mentini (APRE), Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE)
Reviewers	Eglė Butkevičienė (KTU), Ramón Andrés Feenstra (UJI), David Hogan (UCC), Miriam van Loon (AUMC), Matteo Pallocca (UCC), Gaspare Quattrocchi (Luiss), Konstantina Tsimpita (AUTH).
Abstract	This deliverable presents the outcomes of the seven Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops conducted within the CATALISI project to support institutional transformation in European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The MMLs enabled mutual exchange, peer learning, reflection and co-creation among HEIs and selected external stakeholders, focusing on key intervention areas such as Open Science, Citizen Science, Research Culture, Sustainability in research, Reform of research assessment, Research careers and Public engagement. The report highlights the methodological approach, key results, lessons

	learned and recommendations for future implementation of mutual learning as an effective acceleration service for HEIs' institutional transformation.
Keywords	Knowledge sharing; mutual learning; institutional transformation; co-creation; good practices exchange; action plans; transformational pathways; Higher Education Institutions; peer-to-peer learning; European Research Area; institutional cooperation.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	03/06/2025	First draft of the document	Stefania Laneve (APRE), Laura Mentini (APRE)
0.2	10/06/2025	Second draft of the document shared with project's partners	Stefania Laneve (APRE), Laura Mentini (APRE), Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE)
0.3	23/06/2025	Integration of feedback and comments provided by project's partners	Stefania Laneve (APRE)
1.0	26/06/2025	Final version submitted	Stefania Laneve (APRE)

CATALISI consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA	APRE	ITALY
2	EY ADVISORY SPA	EY	ITALY
3	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IRELAND
4	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	BELGIUM
5	KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	KTU	LITHUANIA

6	UNIVERSITAT JAUME I DE CASTELLON	UJI	SPAIN
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITA' INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	ITALY
8	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	POLAND
9	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	UCC	IRELAND
10	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	GREECE
11	STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	NETHERLANDS

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, entitled “*Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report*”, has been developed within the framework of the CATALISI project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement No. 101094917).

The report presents the outcomes of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) activities carried out under Task 2.3, coordinated by APRE. Through the implementation of seven in-person workshops hosted by universities across Europe, each addressing one or more key intervention areas identified as priorities for institutional transformation, this task fostered active, structured knowledge sharing and mutual learning among the participating Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), referred to as the CATALISI implementers.

The MML workshops were conceived as collaborative spaces for reflection, peer exchange and co-creation, enabling HEIs to present concrete experiences, receive targeted feedback, and jointly design actionable strategies tailored to their specific needs for institutional change. Where relevant, external stakeholders from the quadruple helix were also involved, contributing valuable insights and broadening the scope of dialogue.

The results clearly demonstrate that the MML methodology is both effective and adaptable in supporting institutional transformation in the field of Research and Innovation (R&I) as well as in nurturing cooperation between HEIs across Europe for the knowledge and research valorisation. It fosters meaningful dialogue within institutions, promotes ownership of change processes and generates tangible outcomes, such as updated action plans, enhanced stakeholder engagement strategies and improved alignment between strategic priorities and operational practices. While strong academic participation reflects the HEI-centred design of the workshops, the experience also underscored the importance (and challenge) of engaging external actors more systematically, particularly in the later stages of transformation.

Drawing from the insights gained through the MMLs, several recommendations emerge to enhance the role of mutual learning as a strategic enabler of change. Future MML initiatives should broaden stakeholder diversity, particularly beyond academia when appropriate; adopt greater language flexibility and online or hybrid formats to improve accessibility; and seek to institutionalise mutual learning practices within university governance structures, rather than treating them as isolated events. Furthermore, ensuring adequate organisational and facilitation capacities and support and long-term institutional commitment is crucial for successful implementation and sustaining impact.

Overall, the MML workshops—implemented as part of the broader acceleration service “*Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building & outreach*”—proved to be a powerful lever for change. Beyond fostering peer exchange, they contributed to embedding a culture of openness, strategic collaboration, and continuous learning within and between the participating institutions, ultimately supporting the advancement of a more integrated and responsive European Research and Education Area.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Table of content

1. Introduction	9
1.1. Background and aim of CATALISI.....	9
1.2. Aim and structure of the deliverable.....	11
2. Organisation and approach of the MML workshops.....	12
2.1. Related work	12
2.2. Content and methodology of the MML workshops	13
2.2.1. Format	17
2.2.2. Planning and preparation work	18
3. Overview of the 7 MML workshops.....	21
3.1. MML workshop on <i>advancing towards responsible research practices</i> (UJI).....	21
3.1.1. Details of the event.....	21
3.1.2. Thematic Focus and aim of the workshop.....	21
3.1.3. Activities performed.....	22
3.1.4. Concrete achievements for UJI's institutional transformation	23
3.2. MML workshop on <i>stimulating responsible conduct of research</i> (AUMC).....	24
3.2.1. Details of the event.....	24
3.2.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	24
3.2.3. Activities performed.....	25
3.2.4. Concrete achievements for AUMC's institutional transformation	28
3.3. MML workshop on <i>universities' third mission</i> (Luiss).....	29
3.3.1. Details of the event.....	29
3.3.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	30
3.3.3. Activities performed.....	30
3.3.4. Concrete achievements for Luiss institutional transformation	32
3.4. MML workshop on <i>improving research culture: financial sustainability in research</i> (UCC)	33
3.4.1. Details of the event.....	33
3.4.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	34
3.4.3. Activities performed.....	34
3.4.4. Concrete achievements for UCC's institutional transformation	36
3.5. MML workshop on <i>participatory research practices: infrastructure and strategic guidelines</i> (KTU).....	37
3.5.1. Details of the event.....	37
3.5.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	37
3.5.3. Activities performed.....	38
3.5.4. Concrete achievements for KTU's institutional transformation.....	40

3.6.	MML workshop on <i>integrating open citizen science in universities: building stakeholder engagement and living lab ecosystems</i> (AUTH).....	41
3.6.1.	Details of the event.....	41
3.6.2.	Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	42
3.6.3.	Activities performed.....	42
3.6.4.	Concrete achievements for AUTH's institutional transformation	44
3.7.	MML workshop on <i>social engagement in higher education. Building stakeholders cooperations and reaching out to external partners</i> (UG).....	45
3.7.1.	Details of the event.....	45
3.7.2.	Thematic focus and aim of the workshop.....	45
3.7.3.	Activities performed.....	46
3.7.4.	Concrete achievements for UG's institutional transformation	47
4.	Key results of the MML implementation as acceleration service: data & reflections.....	49
4.1.	Quantitative insights	49
4.1.1.	Participants	49
4.1.2.	Intervention Areas	51
4.1.3.	Evaluation.....	52
4.2.	Qualitative outcomes and perspectives	53
4.2.1.	Success factors of the MML approach.....	53
4.2.2.	Benefits for the HEIs' transformational pathways.....	54
4.2.3.	Limitations and Areas of improvements	54
5.	Conclusions.....	55
6.	References	57
	APPENDIX A.....	58
	APPENDIX B.....	74
	APPENDIX C.....	122

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1 – Frontal session – MML workshop: advancing towards responsible research practices in UJI.....</i>	<i>22</i>
<i>Figure 2 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: advancing towards responsible research practices in UJI</i>	<i>23</i>
<i>Figure 3 – Frontal session – MML workshop: stimulating responsible conduct of research at AUMC</i>	<i>26</i>
<i>Figure 4 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: stimulating responsible conduct of research at AUMC</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>Figure 5 – Examples of posters showcased during the poster session</i>	<i>28</i>

<i>Figure 6 – Frontal session – MML workshop: universities' third mission.....</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>Figure 7 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: universities' third mission.....</i>	<i>32</i>
<i>Figure 8 – Keynote speeches.....</i>	<i>32</i>
<i>Figure 9 – Frontal session – MML workshop: financial sustainability in research</i>	<i>35</i>
<i>Figure 10 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: financial sustainability in research</i>	<i>36</i>
<i>Figure 11 – Frontal session – MML workshop: participatory research practices</i>	<i>39</i>
<i>Figure 12 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: participatory research practices</i>	<i>40</i>
<i>Figure 13 – Guided tour to campus facilities – MML workshop: participatory research practices.....</i>	<i>40</i>
<i>Figure 14 – Guided tour to AUTH's library.....</i>	<i>42</i>
<i>Figure 15 – Frontal session – MML workshop: integrating open citizen science in universities: building stakeholder engagement and living lab ecosystems</i>	<i>43</i>
<i>Figure 16 – Co-creation session – MML workshop: integrating open citizen science in universities: building stakeholder engagement and living lab ecosystems</i>	<i>44</i>
<i>Figure 17 – Stakeholder participation in MML workshop by sector (%).....</i>	<i>50</i>
<i>Figure 18 – Chart illustrating position held by academia's participants</i>	<i>51</i>
<i>Figure 19 – Intervention areas of the MML workshop organised.....</i>	<i>51</i>
<i>Figure 20 – Chart illustrating evaluation results.....</i>	<i>52</i>

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table 1 – OVERVIEW OF THE CATALISI DOMAINS AND INTERVENTION AREAS</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Table 2 – OVERVIEW OF THE MML WORKSHOPS' FOCUS AND CONNECTION WITH HEIS' ACTION PLANS</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>Table 3 – DETAILS OF THE UJI MML WORKSHOP.....</i>	<i>21</i>
<i>Table 4 – DETAILS OF THE AUMC MML WORKSHOP</i>	<i>24</i>
<i>Table 5 – DEATAILS OF THE LUISS MML WORKSHOP</i>	<i>30</i>
<i>Table 6 – DETAILS OF THE UCC MML WORKSHOP.....</i>	<i>34</i>
<i>Table 7 – DETAILS OF THE KTU MML WORKSHOP</i>	<i>37</i>
<i>Table 8 – DETAILS OF THE AUTH MML WORKSHOP</i>	<i>41</i>
<i>Table 9 – DETAILS OF THE UG MML WORKSHOP.....</i>	<i>45</i>

ABBREVIATIONS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
CoP	Community of Practice
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GNP	Gross National Product
HEI	Higher Education Institution
LL	Living Labs
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
QH	Quadruple-helix
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND AIM OF CATALISI

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the EU have been recognized for their global leadership in the fields of Research and Innovation (R&I). In order to reinforce their role as drivers of change, in alignment with the European Research Area (ERA) policy objectives¹ and the institutional Higher Education Transformation Agenda² and maximize their research impact, the European Commission pushed to take action by developing strategies, tools and services that can help HEIs in drawing up roadmaps for institutional changes contributing to a new governance framework responding to societal missions.

In line with the European Commission's call to action, CATALISI aims to help and support HEIs to address this complex challenge and implement a successful strategy and individual pathways for institutional transformation in the field of R&I through the adoption of acceleration services. The ultimate aim is to facilitate a way in which HEIs can cooperate more effectively (i.e. through the European universities alliances) in order to better address and solve societal, scientific and economic challenges.

Institutional changes within HEIs will entail a transformation of their governance systems, particularly in the long-term, by addressing both social (e.g. mindset of people inside the organisation) and organisational (e.g. norms, protocols, procedures, policy) dimensions. To support this transformation, CATALISI has identified three domains of intervention and seven acceleration services. Each domain comprises specific intervention areas that alone or combined can stimulate the institutional changes needed to enhance R&I performance and maximise the value of research and its impact across the EU. The three interlinked domains, along with their intervention areas and focus are outlined below.

DOMAINS	INTERVENTION AREAS	FOCUS
Research careers & Talent support	Recognition of qualifications & research careers	This domain and its related intervention areas focus on enhancing the quality of knowledge production as well as developing policies that promote the attractiveness and inclusiveness of researcher careers in the field of R&I. Changes and reforms in these areas are essential to supporting career development, fostering skills acquisition and inclusive and dynamic
	Reform of research assessment	
	Digitisation of higher education sector	
	Supporting talent circulation/mobility	
	Accurately addressing lifelong learning	

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628>.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

	Strengthening of human capital	working environments across the ERA.
	Gender equality & inclusiveness	
Research Modus Operandi	Mainstreaming of Open Science	This domain and its related intervention areas focus on transforming and improving how research is conducted, disseminated and connected to society. This is essential to create a more open, collaborative and impactful research ecosystem .
	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges	
	Reinforcing the role of HEIs in local innovation ecosystems	
	Sharing of research infrastructures and capacities	
Sustainable research and education	Sustainability in education (funding opportunities)	This domain and its related intervention areas focus on developing strategies to improve access to funding opportunities at EU, national and regional level, strengthening research and innovation excellence and capacity.
	Sustainability in research	
	Sustainability in campus operations	

TABLE 1 – OVERVIEW OF THE CATALISI DOMAINS AND INTERVENTION AREAS

To support and facilitate the transformation across one or more of these domains and intervention areas, the CATALISI Consortium has developed a set of **seven acceleration services**. These include the Living Lab, which provides the overarching framework in which the full transformation is envisioned and implemented; the Design Lab for transformational pathways; the Counselling service; a Capacity building & Outreach programme; a Predictive study on skills anticipation; the Marketplace; and the Community of Practice (CoP). The ultimate goal is to empower CATALISI implementers³ to not only apply and use these services in their own institutional contexts, but also to evolve into service providers within the intervention areas that they have acquired expertise.

³ CATALISI model is built upon two blocks: on one side, four facilitators (APRE, EY, ENoLL, F6S) that are responsible for accelerating and facilitating the transformational pathways of HEIs through the provision of acceleration services. On the other side there are the implementers who are the HEIs participating in the project and that are pursuing institutional transformations, namely Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), University Jaume I of Castellon (UJI), Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (Luiss), Gdansk University (UG), University College Cork (UCC), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) and Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC).

The methodology of CATALISI strongly relies on all these acceleration services as integrated tools for facilitating change. Among them, the capacity building & outreach service – formed of three main activities: the development of a Learning Hub; the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops; the implementation of the Twinning schemes - proved to be particularly effective.

Within the CATALISI project, knowledge sharing and mutual is considered a learning method paramount for the achievement of the overall objective of the project, namely to support institutional change of HEIs in the field of R&I. In particular, the MML activities, which are the focus of this report, have contributed significantly to:

- Providing partners with practical knowledge, concrete examples and inputs to achieve and manage institutional transformation over time in the areas of transformation they deem necessary.
- Connecting different HEIs across Europe and other societal actors, share knowledge and good practices and co-create actions that facilitate institutional changes and improve the tailored pathways of each implementing organization.

1.2. AIM AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive report of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) activities carried out under *Task 2.3 – Multi-level knowledge transfer among the implementers*. In particular, the report aims to also evaluate the effectiveness of the MML methodology⁴ as an acceleration service to support institutional transformation in HEIs, in alignment with the overall objectives of the CATALISI project.

Building on the framework set out in *D2.1 – Knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan*, this deliverable highlights the main achievements, strengths, challenges and lessons learned emerging from the seven MML workshops organised and attended by CATALISI implementers. It also offers insights into how the mutual learning approach has contributed to shaping and advancing the tailored transformational pathways of each participating HEI.

This deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 – Introduction outlines the background and rationale of the CATALISI project and outlines the role of MML workshops within the broader set of acceleration services.

Chapter 2 – Organisation and approach of the MML workshops explains how the MML activities are interconnected with the work carried out in other work packages and describes the design and implementation process by APRE and CATALISI implementers.

Chapter 3 – The 7 onsite MML workshops provides a detailed overview of each of the seven workshops, including their thematic focus, structure and main achievements.

Chapter 4 – Key results of the MML implementation: data and reflections presents an analysis of the data and feedback collected from the workshops to assess the overall effectiveness of the MML methodology, along with reflections on its impact.

⁴ For more details about the MML methodology, please refer to *D2.1 – Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393609>

Chapter 5 – Conclusions summarises the main findings of the report and outlines strategic considerations for the future application and upscaling of the MML approach.

2. ORGANISATION AND APPROACH OF THE MML WORKSHOPS

2.1. RELATED WORK

The MML workshops implemented under *Task 2.3 – Multi-level knowledge transfer among the implementers* build upon a series of complementary activities carried out under other CATALISI's Work Packages, namely WP1 and WP3. These activities provided valuable inputs that supported the design, implementation and focus of the MMLs.

On the one hand, *Task 1.1 – Setting-up the CATALISI Acting-Living Labs* and *Task 1.2 – CATALISI Living Labs: exploration stage* played a crucial role in establishing a common understanding among implementers. Through a series of workshops organised by ENOLL, these tasks supported the initial mapping of HEIs' transformation needs, facilitated the identification of relevant intervention areas and of key barriers, challenges and opportunities related to institutional change. These early collaborative exchanges also helped identify the internal and external stakeholders who would later play an active role in the MML workshops.

On the other hand, in the context of *Task 3.2 – Design Lab for transformational pathway: strategy and agenda setting*, EY provided CATALISI implementers with a Reflection Tool. This was an adapted version of the tool developed by the TIME4CS project⁵, which was reviewed to better fit the needs and context of CATALISI.

The Reflection tool was designed to support implementers in the development of personalised transformational pathways aimed at driving institutional change in the field of R&I. Specifically, the tool served as an initial framework for drafting concrete actions and starting to define the short, medium and long-term objectives within each HEIs' transformation strategy.

It provides structured guidance to implementers in articulating their overarching vision, identifying key stakeholders, defining success criteria for planned actions and recognising potential obstacles and required resources. Moreover, the tool facilitates the creation of an implementation timeline outlining the necessary steps toward achieving sustainable institutional change. It also helps implementers in identifying the most suitable acceleration services to support their transformation journey.

Alongside these contributions, the *D2.1 – Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan* provided the formal methodological framework for the design and implementation of the MML workshops. According to the developed methodology, each implementer – namely, Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), University Jaume I of Castellon (UJI), Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli (Luiss), Gdansk University (UG), University College Cork (UCC), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) and Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC) – organised one in-person workshop at their premises, focusing on one or more selected intervention areas. Each implementer also had to attend

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7022933>

the onsite workshop of the others (for a total of seven workshops organised and attended by each organisation). The workshops were co-designed with the support of APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea, as task leaders and facilitators of this activity, ensuring their smooth and effective implementation.

2.2. CONTENT AND METHODOLOGY OF THE MML WORKSHOPS

The results of the workshops carried out under WP1, together with the outcomes of the Reflection Tool exercise and the insights gathered during the meetings conducted by EY in the initial phase of the project (June 2023), were jointly analysed to identify both shared and institutions' specific priorities across the implementers. These activities aimed to refine and validate the selections of the domains and intervention areas in which each HEI would pursue institutional change. The ultimate aim of this analysis was also to optimise the MML workshops' content and usefulness, particularly by focusing on the selected intervention areas and by identifying the most relevant speakers and stakeholders with a potential interest or role in the specific topic.

According to *D2.1 - Knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan*, which provided implementers with a practical guide outlining the steps to follow in the organisation of a MML workshop, the topics were selected by implementers based on their specific needs and priorities with regard to their respective intervention area. A detailed overview of the intervention areas and specific content selected by each implementer for their respective MML workshop is provided below, along with an indication of how these choices align with the Action Plans developed by each institution⁶:

IMPLEMENTER	INTERVENTION AREA(S)	THEMATIC FOCUS OF THE MML WORKSHOP	RELATED ACTIVITY(IES) IN THE ACTION PLAN	SHORT- TO MEDIUM-TERM GOAL
UJI	<p>Reform of research assessment.</p> <p>Recognition of qualifications & research careers.</p> <p>Mainstreaming of Open Science.</p>	Responsible research evaluation practices and research ethics.	<p>Transform or adapt the internal evaluation system of UJI to seek a balance between qualitative and quantitative criteria in scientific assessment. Redefining UJI evaluation "scale".</p> <p>Reviewing (and transforming) the functioning of UJI's ethic</p>	<p>Review of UJI's evaluation policies.</p> <p>Reviewing the ethical committee for research.</p>

⁶ Note that the activities and goals listed in Table 2 are based on the Action Plans_v2 and may therefore slightly differ from the ones included in D1.2 - Acting-LLs action plans.

			committees for research.	
AUMC	<p>Reform of research assessment.</p> <p>Recognition of qualifications & research careers.</p>	How to stimulate a responsible conduct of research (RCR), research culture and research integrity.	<p>Research culture KPIs – Qualitative interview study on stimulating a positive research culture at VU Amsterdam and Amsterdam UMC.</p> <p>Develop an overview of all Research Integrity training available at VU and AUMC.</p> <p>Stimulate and further support the development and re-design of RCR PhD courses.</p>	Embedding Research Integrity (RI) education to increase RCR and research culture.
Luiss	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.	“Third Mission” activities connected to research with a particular focus on research valorisation and societal engagement.	<p>Launch of questionnaires on the awareness on Third Mission in general and on what Luiss does in the field with the goal of monitoring the awareness of the Faculty and of the administrative staff.</p> <p>Training for the faculty on the topics of communication of research and public engagement, also with the goal to participate to European funding activities.</p>	Enhanced quality of Third Mission activities done in Luiss with the active involvement of the faculty with particular regard to public engagement activities.

			Update of the Luiss strategic documents to include objectives with regard to Third Mission's application to the MSCA and Citizens Action calls.	
UCC	Sustainability in research	Financial sustainability for research from a European, national (Irish) and local/institutional level.	<p>Explore, identify and articulate financing issues for sustainability in research.</p> <p>Co-create revised overhead model.</p> <p>Co-create engaged research funding model.</p> <p>Co-create and pilot new income models.</p> <p>Co-create and pilot strategic research fund.</p>	To establish a diverse and resilient research funding model that ensures long-term financial sustainability, supports a positive research culture and aligns with institutional values and strategic priorities.
KTU	Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.	Participatory research practices with a strong focus on Citizen Science.	<p>Organise trainings for KTU researchers and public to increase awareness about Citizen Science.</p> <p>Organise public lectures for society to raise awareness about public engagement in science.</p> <p>To develop a roadmap on how to effectively</p>	Strengthening the activities of the Citizen Science Hub.

			engage public in research.	
AUTH	<p>Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.</p> <p>Mainstreaming of Open Science and digitisation of research.</p>	<p>Integration of Open Science and Citizen Science in universities. Stakeholder engagement and Living Labs.</p>	<p>Review the existing policies and procedures related to qualification acknowledgement and professional advancement.</p> <p>Map out the comprehensive processes involved in qualification recognition, career progression and associated administrative procedures.</p> <p>Providing training sessions for users, particularly researchers, on the principles and practices of data sharing.</p>	<p>Providing certifications and accreditation to individuals involved in Living Labs and Citizen Science projects.</p>
UG	<p>Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.</p> <p>Reinforcing the role of universities in local innovation systems.</p>	<p>Engagement with external stakeholders and building of long-lasting partnerships with actors external to academia (es. Businesses, schools, NGOs, public institutions).</p>	<p>Thesis preparation.</p> <p>Designing and launch of the Citizen Science Lab.</p>	<p>Fostering collaboration between academia and businesses and between students and companies through the development of commissioned dissertations addressing business needs.</p>

TABLE 2 – OVERVIEW OF THE MML WORKSHOPS' FOCUS AND CONNECTION WITH HEIS' ACTION PLANS

It is also worth noting that the final Intervention Areas selected by implementers as the focus of the MML workshops differ from those presented in the preliminary overview chart included in *D2.1 - Knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan* (p. 15). This divergence is primarily the result of the reflection process (through the Reflection Tool) as well as of the work carried out in *T1.1 - Setting up the CATALISI Acting-Living Labs* and *T1.2 - CATALISI Living Labs: exploration stage*. In fact, these tasks enabled a detailed analysis of local contexts, involving stakeholders in defining specific needs, barriers, expectations and objectives, ultimately leading to a more accurate and evidence-informed identification of the areas necessitating interventions.

2.2.1. Format

The format of the MML workshops was initially defined during the proposal writing stage and better detailed and refined during the drafting of D2.1. The intention was to find a format that would optimise and facilitate effective knowledge sharing and mutual learning among implementers, by leveraging both commonalities and differences across institutional contexts. At the same time, the format needed to ensure meaningful, context-specific exchanges that would enable each hosting HEI to collect actionable insights and concrete recommendations on how to drive and manage institutional transformation over time. To meet these goals, the format of the MML workshops was built around the following elements:

- Seven on-site MML workshop, each hosted and organised by one of the implementing HEIs and focused on the specific Intervention Area(s) identified as central to their institutional transformation. Each MML workshop was attended by all other implementers, APRE (as facilitator) and the relevant internal and external stakeholders, identified starting from the mapping carried out in the framework of *T1.1 - Setting up the CATALISI Acting-Living Labs*. Moreover, to accommodate the needs of some implementers (sometimes unable to travel due to academic commitments), the format of the MML workshops was slightly revised and adjusted during implementation: in some cases, a hybrid mode was adopted, enabling online participation and ensuring flexibility.
- Each MML workshop was structured in two main parts:
 - A **frontal session** where the host implementer had to present their experience of institutional transformation, highlighting progress and on-going efforts related to their selected Intervention Area(s). This session aimed to highlight specific institutional challenges, strategies adopted and good practices and often included contributions from internal and/or external stakeholders (e.g. low-, mid- and high-level institutional managers), who provided additional perspectives and first-hand insights.
 - A **co-creation session** tailored around the specific challenges, questions or needs identified by the hosting implementer. This interactive part allowed in-depth peer exchange and joint reflection among all participants, with the aim of generating possible solutions, action pathways and strategic recommendations. Depending on the stage of advancement of each implementer in their institutional transformation process, the co-creation session served one or more of the following purposes:
 - To provide implementers with inputs and possible solutions for challenges encountered or identified in their on-going institutional

transformation process, with the support of local actors and peer institutions.

- To discuss the achievements, impacts and sustainability of the implemented actions.
 - To foster the generation of new knowledge and ideas for all participating HEIs, enabling them to apply relevant insights to their own institutional context and transformation roadmap.
- To assess the effectiveness of each workshop and gather valuable feedback, an **evaluation questionnaire** was finally distributed to participants within one week after the conclusion of each MML workshop through e-mail exchange. This feedback contributed to understanding the perceived relevance and impact of the activity and to continuously improving the design of MML activities and approach in the project.

Moreover, at discretion and initiative of the hosting implementers, several MML workshops were further enriched with complementary activities designed to enhance engagement and contextual learning. These included guided tours of university facilities, keynote speeches and opportunities for live participation in ongoing institutional events and initiatives, offering participants an immersive experience of the host institution's ecosystem and transformation efforts.

2.2.2. Planning and preparation work

The planning and preparation of the MML workshops was coordinated by APRE, in close collaboration with the implementers. Following the agreement on the timeframes and exact dates for hosting the workshops at each implementer's location, APRE provided continuous and individualised support and guidance throughout the entire preparatory process, which was key to ensure the success and smooth implementation of the workshops.

BEFORE THE MML WORKSHOPS

1. **Identification of the topic and expected outcomes:** APRE supported each implementer - through bilateral meetings when necessary - in identifying a specific topic within the selected intervention area. The objective was to clearly define the problem requiring further exploration and to formulate potential solutions with the active involvement of participants. Particular attention was also given by APRE to the early definition of expected outcomes, which proved essential in structuring guiding questions and selecting the most relevant participants and stakeholders.
2. **Identification of stakeholders and participants:** based on the topic and the desired outcomes, the hosting HEI identified relevant participants in order to ensure the most productive environment. Following APRE's recommendations to limit the number of attendees (typically between 15 and 30), in order to ensure active participation, invitees were selected from among the following categories:
 - a. Internal stakeholders across different hierarchical levels (low, middle and top-level managers). Hierarchical levels have been involved since the process of knowledge sharing is intended to be multilevel within institutions. Involving top-level managers in MML workshops as speakers or participants is key to achieve organizational change in universities, by putting pressure on modifying the organizational structures (norms, procedures and protocols).

- b. Organisation's members beyond the project's team to ensure cooperation between different HEIs offices, areas and departments.
 - c. External actors from the quadruple-helix (where relevant) to guarantee a meaningful and useful exchange between the academia and outside realm.
 - d. Experts for keynote speeches, where appropriate, to enrich discussions with their expertise and experiences.
3. **Development of the agenda and activities:** APRE worked with the implementers to structure the agenda and to define the activities according to the format described in the paragraph above. A particular focus was placed on the design of the co-creation session, including the selection of appropriate co-creation techniques⁷ and the formulation of guiding questions tailored to the HEI's specific goals.
 4. **Preparation of the evaluation questionnaire:** APRE developed an example of questionnaire composed of both closed and open-ended questions to be distributed to the workshop's attendees. The aim was to gather feedback and assess the workshop's perceived relevance and impact, especially among stakeholders external to the project.

DURING THE MML WORKSHOPS

1. **Onsite facilitation:** during the implementation phase, APRE was responsible for presenting the CATALISI project and supporting the host HEI in facilitating the workshop. Particular emphasis was placed on the co-creation session, during which APRE worked alongside the organisers to moderate group discussions and interactive exercises.

AFTER THE MML WORKSHOPS

1. **Follow-up and reporting:** after each MML workshop, APRE provided the implementers with detailed reporting procedures. A detailed report template was shared to facilitate the collection of quantitative and qualitative data that could help in better understanding the impact and relevance of the "Capacity building & Outreach" acceleration service in supporting HEIs in their transformation path with new skillset and capabilities.

To facilitate the entire planning and preparatory work, a comprehensive toolkit was made available by APRE to all implementers, containing the necessary materials and detailed guidelines to contribute to an effective planning and delivery of each MML workshop. The toolkit (see Appendix C) includes:

- A MML workshop organisation checklist.
- An Agenda template with detailed guidelines for structuring the workshop.

⁷ A list of the different co-creation techniques was provided in D2.1 – Knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan (see Table 49).

- An example of questionnaire to be shared with attendees, including relevant questions to capture their insights and feedback.
- A Report template for the MML workshop, including guiding questions for the evaluation.

3. OVERVIEW OF THE 7 MML WORKSHOPS

In the following sections, an overview of the content of each MML workshop is provided together with the main points discussed and the summary of key messages. The detailed MML workshop reports are available in Appendix B.

3.1. MML WORKSHOP ON ADVANCING TOWARDS RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH PRACTICES (UJI)

3.1.1. Details of the event

Title of the event	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Advancing Towards Responsible Research Practices in UJI</i>
Partner	Universitat Jaume I (UJI)
Location	Universitat Jaume I (UJI)
Date	19th January 2024
Duration	1 day
Number of Participants	25 participants

TABLE 3 – DETAILS OF THE UJI MML WORKSHOP

3.1.2. Thematic Focus and aim of the workshop

The workshop organised by UJI aimed to foster knowledge exchange and mutual learning around responsible research practices and research ethics within HEIs and to collectively reflect on how to move towards a more open, ethical and responsible research system. Its primary goals were to showcase UJI's progress and challenges in research ethics and integrity, highlight successful practices from other universities and collaboratively explore actionable improvements—particularly regarding Open Access (OA) and the functionality of the ethics committee at UJI.

Specifically, the workshop was designed to:

- Present UJI's achievements and on-going efforts in promoting responsible research practices and improving research integrity.
- Share successful models and tools developed by other universities and institutions, such as Universidad Miguel Hernández and the ETHNA System project.
- Facilitate group discussions on potential strategies to further Open Access (OA) and improve the performance and communication of UJI's ethics committee.

- Identify actionable steps and challenges towards institutional transformation in these domains.

The session also offered a platform to address ethical concerns arising from emerging technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence, and how these intersect with research integrity.

3.1.3. Activities performed

In line with the MML methodology and the defined format, the workshop organized by UJI was structured into two main sessions:

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

The initial session featured insights from three invited speakers, representing internal and external stakeholders, who have actively engaged with institutional reforms in research ethics and assessment:

- **Margarita Vergara** (Adjunct Vice-Rector of Research, UJI) outlined UJI's efforts and progress to transform its research assessment frameworks and shared upcoming institutional challenges. The focus was on a series of transformation actions already developed within other UJI's EU projects and that are progressing thanks to the CATALISI project and on national requirements (e.g. implementation of the ENCA – Estrategia Nacional de Ciencia Abierta) posing challenges and necessitating institutional changes and adaptations for its implementation.
- **Elsa González Esteban** (Vice-Rector of Social Policies and member of the CATALISI team) introduced key outcomes and good practices from the ETHNA System project, such as the development of an ethical code of good practices, the set-up and related functioning of an ethics committee, the creation of an ethical hotline for confidential reporting and indicators and processes to monitor ethical standards in research. This experience provided all participants with key and concrete actions, steps and procedures to follow and adopt for the setting-up of an Ethics Committee in their own institutions.
- **Alberto Campos Pastor** (Universidad Miguel Hernández, UMH) presented the IRIU system developed at UMH, a tool to evaluate researchers' alignment with institutional guidelines for responsible research, including links to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

FIGURE 1 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: ADVANCING TOWARDS RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH PRACTICES IN UJI

Co-creation session

The co-creation session, facilitated by the CATALISI team of UJI with the support of APRE representatives, focused on two core issues:

- **Development of Open Access (OA) Indicators:** participants brainstormed feasible ways to implement a scale to measure researchers' adherence to OA policies. Ideas included integrating OA performance into academic evaluations and establishing symbolic recognitions such as an "OA Champion" badge.
- **Improving the work of the Ethics Committee:** the discussion focused on how the Ethics Committee could be more visible, responsive, and effective. Suggestions included:
 - Creating a transparent platform where researchers could track the progress of their submissions.
 - Introducing reporting mechanisms for unethical conduct.
 - Exploring the feasibility of sanctions or penalties in cases of research misconduct.

FIGURE 2 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: ADVANCING TOWARDS RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH PRACTICES IN UJI

3.1.4. Concrete achievements for UJI's institutional transformation

The MML workshop hosted by UJI generated several valuable insights and concrete proposals to advance in institutional change, particularly in the areas of Open Science, Research Ethics and research assessment.

With regards to **Open Access** (OA), participants highlighted the need for both financial investment and cultural change to support structural improvements in OA adoption. Among the actionable ideas discussed were:

- Establishing recognition mechanisms, such as appointing OA champions within departments.
- Promoting PhD mentoring programs to spread good practices among early-career researchers.
- Conducting internal awareness campaigns and training initiatives to emphasize the benefits of Open Access.

Regarding the functioning of the **Ethics Committee**, discussion focused on increasing transparency, communication and enhancing efficiency in operational processes. Suggested actions included:

- Development of an online tracking system for applications submissions and decisions.
- Ensuring that researchers receive real-time updates on the status of their ethics applications.

The feedback collected during the session fed directly into the UJI institutional action plan, developed in collaboration with the Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development (OCIT), UJI's Library and the Vice-Rectorate for Research. As a concrete follow-up, on 12th February 2024, the UJI CATALISI team submitted a formal proposal to the Vice-Rectorate for Research, focusing on the priority areas identified during the MML.

3.2. MML WORKSHOP ON *STIMULATING RESPONSIBLE CONDUCT OF RESEARCH* (AUMC)

3.2.1. Details of the event

Title:	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Stimulating Responsible Conduct of Research</i>
Implementing Partner:	Amsterdam University Medical Center (Amsterdam UMC)
Date:	11 th April 2024
Location:	Amsterdam UMC, Medical Faculty, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Duration:	1 day
Number of Participants:	Approximately 70 participants

TABLE 4 – DETAILS OF THE AUMC MML WORKSHOP

3.2.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The MML workshop organized by AUMC was designed to actively engage researchers and institutional leaders in rethinking the current research culture through shared reflection, practical examples and co-creative sessions.

The day brought together a diverse group of experts, researchers, institutional leaders, and policymakers to discuss and reflect on the ways research culture can evolve, and what mechanisms—both structural and cultural—can support the development of Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) at academic institutions.

The main theme of the workshop was “Stimulating Responsible Conduct of Research and a Positive Research Culture.” The workshop’s twofold goals were:

1. To **share initiatives, tools, and educational strategies** that have been developed across European institutions and within AUMC to foster responsible research behaviours and ethical awareness.
2. To **reflect on and redefine the concept of research culture**, using metaphors as a creative and inclusive method to surface deeply held assumptions and institutional realities.

Specific objectives included:

- Encouraging researchers to articulate their experiences and values related to research culture.
- Generating creative metaphors to make abstract concepts like “culture” more tangible and actionable.
- Identifying practical solutions and strategies for improving the research environment.
- Highlighting the responsibilities of different actors (researchers, institutions, funders) in driving cultural change.
- Gathering insights for future policymaking and the development of educational programs at both institutional and European levels.

The event was deeply embedded in the CATALISI framework, especially concerning capacity building, institutional reflection, and developing a shared European vision for responsible research.

3.2.3. Activities performed

The MML workshop hosted by AUMC combined informative sessions with hands-on, collaborative learning activities. The program was structured around two main sessions and included an interactive poster session, where several initiatives related to responsible research were showcased. The event brought together CATALISI implementers and representatives from the Erasmus+ [ETHICS project](#)⁸, in which Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) is a partner, underscoring the shared thematic focus of the two projects and encouraging cross-project dialogue.

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

⁸ The Ethics project aims to launch a systemic improvement intervention to improve the quality of Georgian University and Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) research by launching measures to adhere to the foundations of high-quality research and excellence.

In this first part, different experts from AUMC provided relevant examples from other projects on RCR, different internal and external networking efforts in support of RCR. Overall, this session aimed to set the stage for the subsequent discussions, by offering a comprehensive overview of current projects, institutional strategies and tools developed to improve Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR).

Key speakers included:

- **Dr. Miriam van Loon** – *Senior Researcher, Amsterdam UMC* introduced the objectives of the workshop within the context of the CATALISI project and outlined Amsterdam UMC's institutional goals for improving research culture and RCR, particularly through sustainable education and policy reform.
- **Prof. Mariëtte van den Hoven** – *Head of Department Ethics, Law and Humanities, Amsterdam UMC* – and **Dr. Krishma Labib** – *Research Integrity and Open Science, RIOS, Amsterdam VU* - presented inspirational examples and tools from other projects on how stimulating RCR and focused on the changes needed and challenges that need to be addressed to improve the RCR within AUMC.
- **Nathalie Trifkovic** – *Policy advisor Research Integrity, VU* – provided an overview of the VU's Research Culture vision and policy. She highlighted how VU created a working environment in which the standards for good research practices are adhered to and informed by the normative framework in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, 2018. The plan is structured around three main pillars including support, organisation and communication.
- **Prof. Lex Bouter** – *Professor emeritus Methodology and Integrity, VU and Chair of World Conference on Research Integrity (WCRI)* – gave a final keynote speech on Open Science and Research Integrity focusing on fake publications and predatory journals and on the cultural change needed to implement Open Science practices.

FIGURE 3 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: STIMULATING RESPONSIBLE CONDUCT OF RESEARCH AT AUMC

Co-creation session: Reflecting on Research Culture

The core of the MML workshop was a highly engaging co-creation session, designed to foster deep reflection on the concept of research culture through three guiding questions:

1. *What metaphor best represents the current research culture?*
2. *What actionable solutions can improve or transform this culture?*
3. *Who is responsible for initiating and sustaining this change?*

Participants were divided into four working groups. Each person noted their ideas using color-coded post-its. These were then clustered and discussed in depth, with facilitators helping to highlight common themes and diverse perspectives.

The use of metaphors uncovered the symbolic and emotional dimensions of research culture within institutions, ranging from images of broken machinery and competitive arenas to more hopeful metaphors like collaborative ecosystems and learning gardens.

While the responsibility for change was largely attributed to institutions, participants also recognised the importance of shared ownership across the research ecosystem, including individual researchers, funders and policymakers.

FIGURE 4 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: STIMULATING RESPONSIBLE CONDUCT OF RESEARCH AT AUMC

Interactive Poster session

The interactive poster exhibition allowed participants to move freely between stations and engage in small-group conversations.

The topics covered included:

- Open Science tools and institutional strategies for their implementation.
- The Research Integrity Online Support (RIOS) system at AUMC, illustrating how researchers use it for self-assessment and ethical reporting.
- RCR training approaches for embedding ethics education into research curricula.
- Examples of research evaluation and recognition practices, focused on redefining academic merit beyond traditional publication metrics.

Participants were invited to reflect on how the tools and practices presented could be adapted to their own institutional contexts and on recommendations for the AUMC team to improve RCR based on the activities and initiatives presented in the different posters.

FIGURE 5 – EXAMPLES OF POSTERS SHOWCASED DURING THE POSTER SESSION

3.2.4. Concrete achievements for AUMC's institutional transformation

Several significant outcomes emerged from the workshop, both in terms of conceptual reflection and practical follow-up.

1. Metaphorical Insights into Research Culture

Participants developed powerful metaphors to describe their perception of current research culture. Metaphors such as “a pressure cooker” (symbolising stress and competitiveness), “a greenhouse” (suggesting growth, but also fragility) and “a hamster wheel” (indicating constant performance pressure without real progress) highlighted both problematic aspects and aspirations for more inclusive, supportive environments. These insights revealed the symbolic, emotional and structural dimensions of research culture across institutions.

2. Actionable Recommendations

Group discussions and poster presentations led to a set of concrete and actionable proposals to support cultural transformation, including:

- Reforming evaluation systems to recognise diverse contributions (e.g. mentoring, collaboration, failure sharing).
- Promoting transparency and openness (e.g. publishing failure cases, organising peer ethics forums).
- Enhancing leadership training on research integrity, supervision and ethics across career stages.

- Improving mental health support for researchers.
- Reducing hierarchical barriers to enable bottom-up innovation and dialogue.
- Strengthening the role of early-career researchers through mentorship, recognition and participatory governance.
- Embedding freedom and integrity as core values in institutional research policies.

These proposals reflected a shared understanding that effective cultural change requires a balance of top-down policies and bottom-up initiatives.

3. Strategic Institutional Impact

Also, in terms of institutional impact, Amsterdam UMC plans to use the MML outcomes in several ways:

1. An **exploratory article** will be written on the use of metaphors in defining research culture and how international perspectives contribute to improving RCR.
2. A follow-up **qualitative study** involving in-depth interviews with researchers across departments will be launched to examine how researchers at Vrije Universiteit and Amsterdam UMC perceive research culture and what they need to foster a more positive environment.
3. **Training and Policy:** the principles identified during the MML workshop will inform future educational RCR programming and institutional policymaking at Amsterdam UMC. Also, AUMC will incorporate recommendations into RCR training programs and institutional transformation plans within the CATALISI project.
4. **Cross-Institutional Collaboration:** given the interest from other HEIs, Amsterdam UMC will share its training methodologies and materials more widely.

4. Cross-Institutional Knowledge Sharing

Finally, several HEIs expressed interest in using Amsterdam UMC's educational tools, and connections were made for future collaboration and exchange of training methodologies.

3.3. MML WORKSHOP ON UNIVERSITIES' THIRD MISSION (LUISS)

3.3.1. Details of the event

Title of the event	Mobilization and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Universities' Third Mission</i>
Partner	LUISS University – Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli
Location	LUISS University Campus, Rome, Italy

Date	17 th October 2024
Duration	1 day

TABLE 5 – DEATAILS OF THE LUISS MML WORKSHOP

3.3.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The MML workshop organized by Luiss was dedicated to exploring the concept of the Third Mission and its related activities, with a particular focus on research valorisation and societal engagement. According to Luiss, the "Third Mission" includes all forms of engagement and communication with external stakeholders and society at large. The workshop pursued two main objectives:

1. To present Luiss's experience in the field of the Third Mission, particularly in relation to research and to share good practices on how to institutionalize and strategically leverage these activities within the research domain.
2. To gain a deeper understanding of how the Third Mission is conceived and implemented across the other implementers' institutions, identifying commonalities and differences and facilitating the exchange of concrete suggestions, tools, processes, and methods to enhance its impact measurement and effectively integrate Third Mission activities into institutional strategies.

3.3.3. Activities performed

The workshop followed a structured agenda combining presentations, interactive co-creation sessions, and keynote speeches:

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

During this session, different representatives of Luiss University, ranging from mid- to top-level management, provided an overview and several examples on how different Luiss offices contribute to Third Mission activities, demonstrating how the Third Mission sector is integrated at different institutional level.

- After institutional greetings by **Dr. Annalisa D'Agostino**, *Head of the Research and Third Mission (RTM) office*, Luiss representatives from R&TM Office provided an overview of Luiss Third Mission strategy, research-related activities and communication actions.
- **Library Services Representatives:** Presentation on Open Access initiatives and repository management supporting research dissemination.
- **Lectures and Seminars Office Representatives:** Overview of public engagement events, academic conferences, and knowledge transfer activities.
- **ESG Office Representative:** Presentation on sustainability initiatives and corporate responsibility in research context.

FIGURE 6 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: UNIVERSITIES' THIRD MISSION

Co-creation session

During the co-creation session, facilitated by LUISS, EY, and APRE, key aspects related to societal engagement within HEIs were explored, through the following questions: *Does Third Mission exist in all universities? What activities are included under this umbrella? Which metrics should measure Third Mission impact? How should data be collected? How can metrics be integrated into university strategy?*

Through an alphabet Ice-breaking activity participants, divided into three groups, worked together to associate Third Mission concepts with each letter of the alphabet, creating a shared vocabulary and common understanding across contexts.

Afterwards, three rotating working groups were created to discuss impact measurement approaches, data collection methodologies and challenges. Participants had the opportunity to share knowledge and experiences on the following aspects:

- Identify quantitative and qualitative indicators for Third Mission success.
- Explore practical approaches to gathering meaningful metrics.
- Address obstacles in obtaining reliable measurements across three core Third Mission areas: Communication of Research (dissemination, public understanding), Commissioned Engaged Research (stakeholder-driven research projects), Public Engagement Projects and Events (direct community interaction).

Each rotation built upon previous groups' contributions, creating a cumulative knowledge that reflected diverse institutional experiences and perspectives. The rotation cycle concluded with representatives presenting key insights from each group. This iterative approach ensured that all participants could contribute to and benefit from the ideas of the other groups.

FIGURE 7 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: UNIVERSITIES' THIRD MISSION

Keynote speeches

The MML workshop ended with two keynote presentations open to external participants. These presentations provided broader contextual frameworks for understanding Third Mission impact in societal challenges:

- **Maria Rosa Mondardini**, *Director of Research & Development, Citizen Science Zurich* (University of Zurich and ETH Zurich) - delivered insights on "*Citizen Science practices and adoption in universities*".
- **Prof. Gianni Riotta**, *Director, Data Lab (LUISS)* – addressed "*Universities contribution in the fight against disinformation*".

FIGURE 8 – KEYNOTE SPEECHES

3.3.4. Concrete achievements for Luiss institutional transformation

The MML workshop hosted by Luiss University produced a range of achievements related to the institutional implementation of the Third Mission. The event contributed to a deeper understanding of engagement frameworks and stimulated cross-institutional dialogue on strategies, tools and organisational approaches.

Key outcomes for Luiss included:

- The development of a **shared vocabulary and improved conceptual clarity** around Third Mission activities, particularly regarding stakeholder engagement and societal impact monitoring;
- **Stronger internal alignment** among Luiss departments working on Third Mission initiatives, enriched by exposure to practices adopted by other HEIs;
- Acquisition of **practical implementation strategies**, including the use of repository systems for Open Access publications and evaluation frameworks to track progress in institutional transformation;
- Identification of the **potential role of emerging technologies**, such as AI-based tools, in enhancing the measurement of societal impact;
- Recognition of the need for more **systematic, sustainable approaches** to stakeholder engagement and long-term impact assessment;
- Increased awareness that effective Third Mission implementation requires **multi-level coordination** and integration with the university's broader strategic objectives.

As part of its follow-up strategy to advance in institutional change in public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges. Luiss has committed to translating these insights into concrete institutional actions, including:

- The development of a **comprehensive impact assessment framework** for Third Mission activities, including KPIs to monitor research valorisation and societal engagement. This framework will be aligned with university strategic planning and informed by the metrics and challenges discussed during the MML workshop.
- The organisation of **internal stakeholder meetings** to further define Third Mission strategies and ensure operational alignment across departments, integrating workshop reflections into actionable plans.
- The **replication of the collaborative learning format** for other contexts. Positive participant feedback highlighted the potential to apply mutual learning methodologies beyond research valorisation, including in administrative, educational, and communication-related domains.

3.4. MML WORKSHOP ON IMPROVING RESEARCH CULTURE: FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH (UCC)

3.4.1. Details of the event

Event title	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Improving Research Culture: Financial Sustainability in Research</i>
Partner	University College Cork (UCC), Ireland
Location	University College Cork Campus

Date	14 th November 2024
Duration	4.5 hours (09:00-13:30 GMT)
Total Participants	15

TABLE 6 - DETAILS OF THE UCC MML WORKSHOP

3.4.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The MML workshop organised by UCC focused on the theme of financial sustainability in research, considered a key determinant of research culture and institutional resilience. UCC identified this as a critical intervention area within its CATALISI Action Plan, given increasing demands on researchers, persistent funding gaps and growing dependency on specific external funders. The workshop addressed the topic from European, national and institutional perspectives and aimed to:

- Enable structured dialogue on research funding systems and sustainability strategies.
- Foster mutual understanding across different institutional and policy contexts.
- Examine the intersection of funding frameworks with Open Science, regulatory mandates and researcher career development.
- Co-create insights to inform the refinement of UCC's Action Plan and broader institutional transformation agenda.

The workshop also served as a space for peer validation of UCC's proposed intervention strategies. Through interactive exchange and feedback mechanisms, implementers from other HEIs and other stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix, including national policy makers, civil society representatives and Irish university associations, provided critical input, helping to strengthen and contextualise UCC's approach to achieving sustainable, balanced and mission-driven research funding.

3.4.3. Activities performed

The MML workshop was structured in two main phases: an initial frontal session featuring expert presentations, followed by a co-creation session.

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

The frontal session was aimed to introduce the topic of financial sustainability by providing a multi-level overview of challenges and opportunities at the European, national (Irish) and institutional (UCC) levels. Contributions included:

- **Enora Bennetot Pruvot**, *Deputy Director of Governance, Funding & Public Policy Development, European University Association (EUA)* delivered a presentation titled "A European Perspective on Financial Sustainability". Drawing on key findings from EUA surveys, she highlighted the systemic financial pressures affecting research-performing organisations in Europe and the long-term sustainability risks associated with growing reliance on competitive external funding.

- **Lisa Keating**, *Director of Research and Innovation, Irish Universities Association*, provided “*An Irish Perspective on Research Culture and Funding*”, offering insights into Ireland’s current policy environment. She discussed challenges such as outdated research infrastructures, low levels of R&D investment relative to GNP and institutional dependence on large-scale research centres.
- **Dr. David O’Connell**, *Director of Research Support and Policy, UCC* presented “*An Institutional Perspective – Challenges and Priorities at UCC*”, outlining internal funding constraints at UCC, including an over-reliance on project-based funding and a narrow overhead distribution model that limits the university’s ability to make strategic reinvestments.

Together, these presentations established a shared knowledge base for subsequent peer exchange, setting the stage for collaborative reflection and the development of actionable strategies during the second phase of the workshop.

FIGURE 9 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH

Co-creation session

The session was introduced by **David Hogan**, *Strategic Planning Lead, UCC and CATALISI Coordinator team*, who presented UCC’s proposed transformation pathways. These focused on improving internal research funding frameworks, enhancing overhead allocation mechanisms, and reinforcing the institutional retention of strategic research funding to support long-term capacity building.

Then, **Martin Galvin** facilitated a peer feedback and dialogue session, encouraging participants to critically examine UCC’s proposed strategies while contributing comparative insights from their own institutional contexts. The discussion extended to funding models and

sustainability challenges in other European countries, including examples from the Netherlands, Spain and Lithuania.

The main objective of this session was to inform the refinement of UCC's intervention strategies through peer interrogation and collaborative problem-solving. Participants explored models and mechanisms for building a financially sustainable research ecosystem capable of supporting diverse research communities and activities across all levels.

To initiate discussion, attendees engaged in a silent ideation exercise, reflecting on key issues raised during the workshop and contextualising them within their national or institutional frameworks. Individual reflections were captured on notes structured to mirror a Miro board template, providing a visual guide for subsequent group exchange.

Importantly, participants collectively chose to move beyond the constraints of the original templates, opting instead for a more open and organic discussion format. This shift enabled deeper and more dynamic dialogue, reinforcing the mutual learning goals of the session.

FIGURE 10 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY IN RESEARCH

3.4.4. Concrete achievements for UCC's institutional transformation

The MML workshop at UCC resulted in a number of concrete achievements, offering actionable insights for both UCC and other CATALISI partners working on institutional transformation in research funding systems.

Identified Institutional Challenges include:

- A national funding gap of over €300M/year.
- Stalled investment in research infrastructure (over 50% of equipment >10 years old).
- Over-reliance on SFI and large-scale research centers (e.g., Tyndall Institute).
- Lack of institutional mechanisms to retain and reinvest overhead funding.

- Talent retention risks due to funding instability and regional brain drain.

Key Outcomes and Actions include:

- Exploring options for institutional-level retention and reinvestment of overheads to ensure financial flexibility and long-term sustainability.
- Identification of a new income stream for research finance thanks to the discussions with the MML participants.
- Integrating the principle of financial sustainability into strategies for researcher attraction, support and career development.
- Initiating a collection of international good practices in sustainable research financing to inform future planning.
- Using the outcomes of the workshop to update and refine UCC's CATALISI Action Plan, strengthening stakeholder engagement and institutional commitment to long-term change. Furthermore, UCC used the MML as an opportunity to showcase and seek feedback on progress against their Action Plan both with CATALISI participants and QH stakeholders.

These results reflect the workshop's dual role as a space for strategic thinking and as a practical accelerator for institutional reform, both within UCC and across the broader CATALISI Consortium.

3.5. MML WORKSHOP ON PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH PRACTICES: INFRASTRUCTURE AND STRATEGIC GUIDELINES (KTU)

3.5.1. Details of the event

Title of the Event:	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Participatory Research Practices at KTU: Infrastructure and Strategic Guideline</i>
Partner	Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)
Date	10 th December 2024
Duration	1 day
Location	KTU Campus, Kaunas, Lithuania
Participants	14

TABLE 7 – DETAILS OF THE KTU MML WORKSHOP

3.5.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The primary focus of the MML workshop organised by KTU was to advance institutional strategies for participatory and citizen science practices. The event also marked a key milestone contributing to the formal presentation of the structure and objectives of the established Citizen Science Hub⁹.

This MML workshop focused on developing and promoting citizen science practices within the university and beyond. Its main goals were:

- Presenting KTU's institutional guidelines on **Citizen Science**, developed to formalize standards for public engagement in scientific research.
- Introducing the vision and role of the KTU **Citizen Science Hub** as a central structure to support participatory approaches.
- Showcasing case studies of citizen science initiatives addressing societal challenges across fields such as urban design, public libraries and youth engagement.
- Exploring interdisciplinary intersections between citizen science and fields such as architecture, design and education.
- Co-creating ideas for embedding citizen science practices into KTU's broader strategic development and educational activities.

This initiative supports KTU's long-term vision of becoming a socially embedded university fostering innovation through community collaboration.

3.5.3. Activities performed

The MML workshop at KTU was structured as a dynamic and interactive full-day event that combined expert presentations, practical case studies, participatory dialogue and immersive site visits.

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

The first session was dedicated to exploring the thematic core of the workshop: participatory research and citizen science. A series of presentations delivered by KTU experts offered insights from both disciplinary and institutional perspectives:

- **Renata Višinskaite**, *manager of R&I projects (KTU)*, introduced the newly developed Citizen Science Guidelines, outlining the key ethical principles, operational standards and methodological recommendations that will guide future citizen science initiatives at the university. These guidelines represent a foundational step toward the formal integration of citizen science practices within KTU's research ecosystem.
- **Eglė Butkevičienė**, *Head of Citizen Science Hub and CATALISI team member (KTU)*, presented the mission, functions and operational structure of the newly launched Citizen Science Hub. Designed as a central coordination platform, the hub supports interdisciplinary collaboration, serves as a resource for researchers and students and facilitates active public engagement.

⁹ The Citizen Science Hub was formally established as a key output of a previous Horizon EU project (TIMES4CS) in which KTU was partner and dedicated to citizen science institutional transformation in HEIs. The Citizen Science Hub at KTU serves as a central platform for organizing and supporting citizen science projects. It plays a key role in encouraging collaboration across different disciplines and provides valuable resources for students, researchers, and members of the public who want to get involved in or lead citizen science efforts.

The session then showcased concrete institutional applications of citizen science:

- **Gintarė Tautkevičienė**, *Director of the KTU Library*, offered insights into how libraries can act as enablers of participatory knowledge creation and dissemination.
- **Kęstutis Zaleckis**, *Chief project researcher*, showcased how citizen science is being employed in the fields of architecture and urban planning, particularly through community-based projects that collect public input on environmental design and urban sustainability.

The event also drew on international case studies from three major EU-funded projects (TIME4CS, YouCount, and LibOCS) demonstrating how citizen science can effectively address social challenges through co-designed research methodologies and inclusive data collection processes.

FIGURE 11 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH PRACTICES

Co-Creation session

During the co-creation session, using a World Café methodology, participants were further invited to reflect on the earlier presentations, share their own institutional experiences and collaboratively explore how participatory research could be strengthened and expanded within the KTU ecosystem.

Key themes discussed during this session included how to support talent mobility (e.g. through Erasmus+), how to build interdisciplinary writing communities via writing clinics and how to better align participatory research initiatives with strategic planning and funding mechanisms.

FIGURE 12 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH PRACTICES

Guided tour to Campus Facilities

The workshop ended with a guided tour of several KTU's innovation and co-creation spaces: the Library, M-Lab and Infinity Lab. These visits offered participants concrete illustrations of how dedicated physical environments and infrastructures can support collaborative research, hands-on experimentation and active engagement with societal stakeholders. The showcased facilities demonstrated KTU's commitment to fostering a research culture grounded in openness, interdisciplinarity and community involvement, reinforcing the institutional vision of a socially embedded university.

FIGURE 13 – GUIDED TOUR TO CAMPUS FACILITIES – MML WORKSHOP: PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH PRACTICES

3.5.4. Concrete achievements for KTU's institutional transformation

The MML workshop led to several immediate and strategic achievements such as:

- The formal validation and adoption of Citizen Science Guidelines as a foundational institutional document to support and regulate public engagement in research.
- The successful launch of the Citizen Science Hub, including the articulation of its strategic mission and operational structure.

- Increased cross-faculty interest and commitment to embedding citizen engagement practices into research.

Building on the momentum generated during the workshop, KTU identified a series of actionable steps to further institutionalize citizen science:

- Design and implementation of a mentorship program for faculty interested in Erasmus mobility and citizen science.
- Development of a writing clinic prototype to foster peer-to-peer collaboration on research writing and publication.
- Creation of a dedicated newsletter or blog to communicate citizen science initiatives and share outcomes.
- Integration of citizen science into institutional research strategies, including its inclusion in strategic planning documents and funding proposals.
- Awareness-raising initiatives to promote the societal relevance and policy alignment of participatory research among researchers and staff.
- Refinement of KTU Action Plan across its three intervention areas informed by MML insights and supported by a strategic briefing to university leadership to ensure alignment and institutional buy-in.

3.6. MML WORKSHOP ON INTEGRATING OPEN CITIZEN SCIENCE IN UNIVERSITIES: BUILDING STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND LIVING LAB ECOSYSTEMS (AUTH)

3.6.1. Details of the event

Title of the Event	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Integrating Open Citizen Science in Universities: Building Stakeholder Engagement and Living Lab Ecosystems</i>
Partner:	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
Date	22 nd January 2025
Duration	1 day
Location	AUTH Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA), Thessaloniki, Greece
Number of participants	25

TABLE 8 – DETAILS OF THE AUTH MML WORKSHOP

3.6.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The MML workshop organised by AUTH aimed to explore how Open Science and Citizen Science can be operationalised within university ecosystems, both from a strategic and practical perspective. The workshop brought together institutional, governmental and community stakeholders to collaboratively address two main questions:

- How can Open and Citizen Science be structurally embedded in universities?
- What frameworks best support sustainable stakeholder engagement?

The event served to:

- Present AUTH's current efforts and aspirations toward institutional transformation.
- Support the co-creation of actionable strategies to inform AUTH's CATALISI transformation pathway.
- Showcasing the Thess-AHALL Living Lab as a successful model of collaborative and socially impactful research that integrates citizens and public actors into the innovation processes.

3.6.3. Activities performed

The MML workshop combined a guided tour with frontal and co-creation sessions.

Guided Tour to AUTH's Library

The day began with a guided tour to the AUTH's Library. The tour offered an in-depth look at the university's efforts to support Open Science through academic infrastructure, highlighting digital resources, open-access repositories and collaborative workspaces that enable knowledge sharing.

FIGURE 14 – GUIDED TOUR TO AUTH'S LIBRARY

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

This session provided an overview of the AUTH's pathway toward openness, while emphasising key goals such as stakeholder engagement, transparency and societal impact.

The session brought together academic and policy experts to present national and institutional strategies, case studies and system-level reflections on Open Science and Citizen Science in Greece:

- **Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis** – *Lab of Medical Informatics Medical School, AUTH*, shared experiences from AUTH's medical research initiatives that integrate citizen participation and health technologies through participatory approaches.
- **Lia Ollandezou** – *Library and Information Center, Coordinator of Hellenic Academic Libraries Link* provided a national overview of Open Science policy implementation, highlighting challenges such as data management, repository harmonisation and the application of FAIR data principles across academic institutions.
- **Prof. Alexander Chatzigeorgiou** – *Department of applied Informatics, University of Macedonia* shared institutional experiences in embedding open practices in teaching and research, particularly within the fields of digital innovation and applied informatics.

This session also addressed barriers to implementation, such as cultural resistance, fragmented policies and lack of awareness among researchers.

Thess-AHALL Living Lab Showcase

Furthermore, representatives from **Thess-AHALL**, AUTH's award-winning Living Lab, demonstrated how real-world societal and health challenges can be addressed through citizen co-creation and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Examples included:

- Collaborative design with older adults;
- Cross-disciplinary teams in clinical and digital health;
- Involvement of non-academic actors in both research and policy development.

This session served as an inspiring good practice, effectively illustrating the potential of Living Labs to bridge academia and society and to institutionalise participatory research approaches within a university's ecosystem.

FIGURE 15 – FRONTAL SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: INTEGRATING OPEN CITIZEN SCIENCE IN UNIVERSITIES: BUILDING STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND LIVING LAB ECOSYSTEMS

Co-Creation session

The co-creation session engaged participants in small group exercises aimed at identifying key institutional challenges and formulating strategic approaches for integrating Open Science and Citizen Science into AUTH's organisational structures and practices.

Topics explored included:

- Strategies for engaging communities in research processes and fostering inclusive collaboration.
- The governance of research data, with a focus on implementing FAIR principles and enhancing the use of institutional repositories.
- Ways to embed open methodologies into teaching and research supervision.
- The development of sustainable institutional frameworks to support public participation in research on a long-term basis.

The co-creation process was seen as highly valuable in surfacing both practical constraints and inspiring new pathways for action.

FIGURE 16 – CO-CREATION SESSION – MML WORKSHOP: INTEGRATING OPEN CITIZEN SCIENCE IN UNIVERSITIES: BUILDING STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND LIVING LAB ECOSYSTEMS

3.6.4. Concrete achievements for AUTH's institutional transformation

The workshop led to several key achievements:

- Greater awareness of the institutional and national infrastructure available to support Open Science implementation.
- Identification of gaps in data governance and stakeholder engagement mechanisms.
- Stronger internal consensus on the need for cultural transformation to mainstream open and participatory research approaches.
- Recognition of Thess-AHALL as a replicable model for effective multi-stakeholder co-creation with societal impact.

Actionable follow-up measures for AUTH institutional strategy and transformational pathway include:

- Development of a roadmap **to improve stakeholder engagement** in research design and dissemination.
- Plans to create institutional frameworks for FAIR data practices and Open Access policy enforcement.
- Exploring opportunities for embedding Citizen Science into curricula and doctoral training.
- Recognition of the need to build internal awareness and training pathways on Open Science principles.

These achievements mark a significant step forward in AUTH's efforts to operationalise openness, foster inclusive research cultures and position citizen engagement as a strategic pillar of institutional transformation.

3.7. MML WORKSHOP ON SOCIAL ENGAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION. BUILDING STAKEHOLDERS COOPERATIONS AND REACHING OUT TO EXTERNAL PARTNERS (UG)

3.7.1. Details of the event

Title of the Event:	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop: <i>Social engagement in Higher Education. Building stakeholders cooperations and reaching out to external partners</i>
Partner:	Gdansk University (UG)
Date:	11 th April 2025
Duration:	1 day
Location:	Faculty of Economics, University of Gdańsk, ul. Armii Krajowej 119/121, 81-824 Sopot
Number of participants:	18

TABLE 9 – DETAILS OF THE UG MML WORKSHOP

3.7.2. Thematic focus and aim of the workshop

The MML workshop organised by UG aimed to explore how universities can strategically and operationally embed societal engagement into their core missions. The workshop served as

both a reflection on UG's current practices and a co-creative space to shape future directions in stakeholder collaboration.

The workshop focused on enhancing societal engagement in higher education, with particular attention to the "third mission" of universities, building meaningful and sustainable collaborations with external stakeholders beyond teaching and research.

Key aims included:

- Showcasing UG's practical models of outreach and external cooperation.
- Enabling mutual learning around the design, delivery and impact of stakeholder engagement strategies.
- Discussing structural barriers and enablers of the third mission.
- Co-creating actionable solutions for improving cooperation with schools, businesses, NGOs and public bodies
- Reflecting on how large-scale educational initiatives like UG's Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad can catalyse impact.

The event positioned societal engagement not merely as a complementarity activity but as a vital function of a university committed to delivering public value.

3.7.3. Activities performed

The MML workshop was conceived as a participatory and experience-based event, combining presentations, live observation and co-creation exercises.

Frontal session on sharing experiences and good practices for institutional change

The frontal session focused on presenting UG's approach to societal engagement.

Key highlights included:

- A comprehensive overview of UG outreach and cooperation models, especially in education and business fields.
- A detailed case study by **Prof. Przemysław Borkowski** on the *Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad*, a national-scale event that annually brings together over 100 high schools, teachers and business partners. The Olympiad was presented as a scalable and replicable model for experiential education and structured stakeholder collaboration.

These presentations helped clarify the institutional, logistical and cultural dimensions of effective outreach programming.

Participatory Observation of the Olympiad

Participants had the opportunity to observe the Olympiad in action, gaining first-hand insights into UG engagement strategy. They visited the competition area, attended associated workshops for teachers and visited UG's laboratory demonstrations.

This live observation gave attendees an immersive experience of how societal engagement unfolds on the ground, including:

- The scale and complexity of multi-stakeholder coordination.
- Interactions between students, academic staff and industry mentors.
- The practical implementation of outreach as a means of strengthening university-society links.

Co-Creation session

In the first part of the co-creation session, participants were divided into breakout groups to identify challenges related to stakeholder engagement. Each group focused on a different stakeholder category (e.g. schools, business, public agencies, NGOs). Commonly identified barriers included:

- Limited staff incentives and resources to support engagement activities.
- Fragmented internal coordination at institutional level.
- Communication gaps between academia and external stakeholders.
- Lack of long-term structured engagement strategies.

A dedicated discussion led by **Prof. Dariusz Tłoczyński**, with contributions from business representatives, explored models of university-business collaboration. Key discussion points included:

- How companies can support HEIs not only financially, but through mentoring, co-teaching and skills development.
- The importance of trust, shared values and co-creation in sustaining partnerships.
- Challenges related to expectations, timelines and knowledge asymmetries.

In the second part of the co-creation session, groups returned to their earlier challenges and collaboratively developed solutions. Proposed ideas included:

- Implementation of stakeholder mapping protocols and dashboards.
- Appointment of faculty-level engagement coordinators.
- Allocation of dedicated funding for outreach roles.
- Creation of alumni networks and business advisory boards.
- Introduction of recognition schemes for academic and administrative staff contributing to third mission activities.

These ideas will feed UG's institutional transformation pathway.

3.7.4. Concrete achievements for UG's institutional transformation

The MML workshop at UG generated both strategic insights and actionable outcomes aimed at reinforcing the institution's third mission and strengthening its engagement with external stakeholders. Strategic achievements:

- Enhanced internal awareness of the third mission's value and impact.

- Identification of structural gaps in stakeholder engagement strategy.
- Deeper understanding of business-university collaboration dynamics.
- Inspiration drawn from peer interaction and live observation.

As a direct result of the workshop discussions and co-creation activities, UG outlined several practical follow-up actions:

- Development of a draft barrier-solution matrix to guide internal reflection and follow-up.
- Plans to systematise external cooperation by appointing faculty-based stakeholder liaisons to coordinate outreach efforts.
- Integration of outreach initiatives into curricula (e.g. via service learning and co-teaching models).
- Formalisation of business and civic engagement through dedicated institutional roles.

4. KEY RESULTS OF THE MML IMPLEMENTATION AS ACCELERATION SERVICE: DATA & REFLECTIONS

4.1. QUANTITATIVE INSIGHTS

In the framework of the CATALISI project, the acceleration service "Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building & outreach" supported the implementers in the organization of 7 MML workshops, conceived as an opportunity to facilitate and accelerate the process of institutional change through a mutual learning exercise among different HEIs across Europe and other societal actors.

The analysis of the main outcomes and reflections presented in the following sections is based on the data collected through multiple sources, ensuring a comprehensive and evidence-based understanding of the MML experience. In particular, the findings draw on:

- The MML Reports compiled by each of the seven implementers who hosted the workshops.
- The evaluation questionnaires completed by external participants.
- A series of informal debriefings conducted during or after the workshops with implementers, offering contextual clarification and deeper reflections.

This mixed-method approach allows for a robust assessment of the methodology's implementation, highlighting its strengths, limitations and potential for replication. The combination of institutional self-assessment and participant feedback provides a well-rounded picture of how mutual learning contributed to the advancement of each HEI's transformation pathway and to the broader objectives of the CATALISI project.

4.1.1. Participants

A total of approximately **190 participants** representing different stakeholders' categories were engaged and took part in the MML workshops¹⁰. The chart below shows the distribution of participants across the different sectors of the quadruple-helix:

¹⁰ The details about the participants to each workshop, including number, sector of belonging and position held, are available in Appendix B.

FIGURE 17 – STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION IN MML WORKSHOP BY SECTOR (%)

As shown in Figure 17, the great majority of stakeholders involved in the MML workshops came from the academia sector. Participation from other sectors was more limited, with 4% representing policy bodies, governmental institutions or Innovation agencies, 3% from industry and 2% from research and technology organisations. While this distribution may appear unbalanced at first glance, it reflects the intentional design of the MML workshops, which were primarily conceived as mutual learning spaces among HEIs involved in the CATALISI Consortium. This HEI-centred focus was central to the methodology: by fostering direct knowledge exchange among implementing universities, the MMLs enabled a deep and targeted reflection on how institutional changes are being approached, piloted and embedded in similar organisational contexts. The peer-to-peer dimension of the workshops proved particularly effective in addressing common challenges, transferable solutions and lessons learned.

At the same time, many workshops also included external experts, often from other EU-funded initiatives, and representatives of quadruple helix stakeholders, contributing diverse insights and enhancing the relevance of discussions. Nevertheless, the limited participation of non-academic actors remains a challenge. In fact, several implementers reported difficulties in identifying and mobilising local external stakeholders, particularly those not traditionally involved in research and innovation ecosystems.

The data underscore a crucial point: Higher Education Institutions themselves emerged as the primary drivers of institutional transformation. The strong presence of academic actors facilitated a deep peer-to-peer dialogue, enabling mutual learning across diverse national contexts. Moreover, the intervention areas and topics selected as the focus of the MML workshops (e.g. Open Science, Third Mission, Research culture) were particularly suited for discussion among HEI representatives, as they required deep institutional reflection and alignment before engaging wider ecosystems. Going forward, expanding participation from external stakeholders would add further value, especially in later stages of transformation.

Among the academic participants, as illustrated by Figure 18, the majority were professors/researchers (72%), soon followed by technical and administrative staff (19%) and top-management bodies (6%).

FIGURE 18 – CHART ILLUSTRATING POSITION HELD BY ACADEMIA'S PARTICIPANTS

This distribution reflects a strong engagement of academic staff directly involved in research and innovation processes, while also highlighting a modest but meaningful participation from institutional leadership, considered essential by CATALISI implementers for aligning transformation processes with strategic governance and for advancing in the transformation pathway.

4.1.2. Intervention Areas

The chart below provides an overall overview of the intervention areas selected by implementers as a focus of the MML workshops:

FIGURE 19 – INTERVENTION AREAS OF THE MML WORKSHOP ORGANISED

The selected intervention areas well reflect the transformational pathways and the action plans of the CATALISI implementers. Notably, some implementers chose to address more than one intervention area within their MML workshop. This was not necessarily the result of an explicit strategic decision, but rather a consequence of the inherently cross-cutting nature of certain topics (such as in the case of Gdansk University), where the chosen theme intersected different areas of institutional change. This overlap highlights the complexity and interdependence of the challenges addressed within the CATALISI framework¹¹.

4.1.3. Evaluation

When evaluating the MML workshops, it is important to distinguish between two perspectives: the assessment provided by each implementer who organised and hosted the event, and the feedback from external participants (those not part of the CATALISI consortium). Regarding the latter, since each implementer was responsible for distributing the evaluation questionnaire and collecting responses, this analysis is based on the feedback and summaries they included in the MML Reports submitted to APRE.

As shown in Figure 20, all implementers except one, rated the MML workshops as *very successful* and all of them expressed a clear intention to replicate the format in the future, for other aims and topics beyond the CATALISI project.

FIGURE 20 – CHART ILLUSTRATING EVALUATION RESULTS

In fact, according to them, the MML methodology and the format proved to be highly effective, as it successfully fulfilled its core purpose: serving as a dynamic learning method for the achievement of the overall objective of the project, namely, to support institutional change of HEIs in the field of R&I. In particular, the implementers emphasised its effectiveness in:

- Facilitating inter- and intra-institutional dialogue.
- Enabling strategic reflections and sharing experiences and recommendations.

¹¹ For a detailed overview of the selected intervention areas and topics and how they are connected with transformational pathways' goals and with the activities of the Action Plans, please refer to Table 2.

- Building networks, synergies, partnerships and cross-functional collaborations (e.g. new consortia for grant applications).

4.2. QUALITATIVE OUTCOMES AND PERSPECTIVES

The use and implementation of the MML methodology within the CATALISI project proved to be a valuable accelerator of institutional change across the HEIs. In fact, throughout the project, the MML workshops served as a participatory space for dialogue, sharing knowledge, reciprocal learning, cross-sectoral collaboration and strategic reflections. Some key dimensions emerge and help to better understand how and why the MML approach can contribute and support HEIs to advance in their transformational pathway.

4.2.1. Success factors of the MML approach

The MML workshops enabled HEIs to step back from daily work and critically examine their internal processes and strategic directions. This reflection was especially valuable where diverse institutional actors (e.g. academic leaders, researchers, technical and administrative staff) were brought together encouraging inclusive participation and cohesion to analyse internal practices and align on strategic goals.

Several key features, repeatedly highlighted by implementers, made the MML methodology widely effective:

- **Participatory design and interactive format:** the co-creation sessions and the use of co-creation techniques (e.g. metaphor-based exercises at AUMC, live observations at UG, world café at KTU, etc) stimulated interaction and reflection and facilitated discussion in formal contexts, thus helping people move beyond hierarchical roles and encouraging them to express ideas and positions more freely, without fear of judgement or error.

The choice of co-creation techniques, ranging from basic to more advanced, was adapted to each implementer's level of familiarity with the MML methodology. Among the most used were brainstorming with idea mapping, the alphabet ice-breaker and World Café sessions, all of which contributed to creating inclusive and creative environments for dialogue.

In some cases, a key strength was the inclusion of experiential components: for instance, at UG, observing a large-scale outreach event (the Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad) helped participants from other HEIs catch good practices for business and societal collaboration.

- **Adaptability to different contexts and needs:** the methodology was flexible enough to be tailored to specific institutional needs, goals and challenges and to a wide range of topics.
- **Peer-learning environment:** the cross-institutional nature of the workshops enabled HEIs to facilitate open discussions, share experiences, concrete recommendations and explore solutions together, also contributing to build a trustful relationship among partners.

- **Focus on relevance and improved understanding of complex topics:** by grounding the discussion in institutional realities, the MMLs ensured that outcomes were directly linked to strategic priorities.

4.2.2. Benefits for the HEIs' transformational pathways

All implementers reported that the MML workshops had a clear and positive impact on the advancement of their institutional transformation pathways. They had the opportunity of collecting key suggestions about concrete actions to be integrated in their Action Plans and transformation roadmaps to achieve real institutional changes in the identified intervention areas. The most evident benefits emerged in the following areas:

- **Alignment of internal strategies:** several implementers (e.g. Luiss, UCC, AUTH), thanks to the MML workshops, clarified their internal priorities, fostered alignment across internal departments and refined their Action Plans through group reflection.
- **Capacity building and awareness-raising:** the workshops contributed to building understanding and engagement around key themes as well as to gathering inputs and practical suggestions from the more experienced implementers in institutional change on a specific topic.
- **Problem identification and solution development:** MML enabled implementers to address specific challenges and co-reflect on possible targeted solutions.
- **HEIs' governance engagement and follow-up mechanisms:** when and where it was possible, the active involvement of top-level management represented a key enabling factor for institutional uptake. In fact, HEIs noted that the participation of vice-rectors, directors or HEIs' representatives actively involved in policy and decision-making processes not only gave strategic legitimacy to the process but also increased the chances of further elaborating and integrating MML outcomes into formal organisational policy decisions. Additionally, HEIs outlined concrete follow-up actions aimed at better shaping their transformation pathways from a concrete point of view.

4.2.3. Limitations and Areas of improvements

Despite the overall success and positive feedback, the implementation of the MML methodology also highlighted areas where improvements are possible, especially with regards to the following aspects:

- **Limited diversity of stakeholders engaged:** while the MML workshops were primarily designed to foster peer learning among the HEIs involved in the CATALISI project, the limited participation of external stakeholders from other sectors of the quadruple helix can be considered a limitation. A broader and more balanced representation across these groups would have enriched the multi-actor dialogue, strengthened the relevance and impact of the discussions and maximised the results.
- **Resources constraints:** some implementers noted that becoming familiar with the MML methodology as well as organising the workshops required dedicated time, resources and facilitation capacity, which are seen as a potential challenge for under-resourced teams in the future.
- **Need to institutionalise the MML approach** and embed it into the HEIs' governance culture to ensure its long-term sustainability.

- **Need to adapt the MML methodology for online format:** while the in-person format enabled rich interaction and peer learning, several implementers reported logistical challenges (e.g. travel barriers or scheduling conflicts) that limited broader participation. Developing a flexible, well-structured online version of the MML methodology could ease implementation, improve accessibility for a wider range of stakeholders and increase inclusiveness. Moreover, an online format could allow for more frequent, modular learning exchanges, complementing the intensity of face-to-face sessions with sustained engagement over time.
- **Language flexibility:** while English was used as the working language to ensure alignment with the international nature of the project, some implementers (e.g. UG, UJI) noted that this may have limited the engagement of local stakeholders, in particular civil society organisations, SMEs and public sector actors less accustomed to working in English. Allowing for the use of local languages or offering simultaneous translation, when possible, could significantly enhance interaction, inclusiveness and the quality of contributions from a more diverse range of participants. This is particularly relevant when the workshop aims to stimulate dialogue with territorial stakeholders and ensure community ownership of transformation processes.

These recommendations would further strengthen the methodology's impact and scalability and would unlock the full transformative potential of mutual learning across diverse institutional and territorial contexts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Within the CATALISI project, the implementation of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops, one of the three pillars of the broader acceleration service "*Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building & outreach*", has demonstrated the strategic relevance and added value of mutual learning as an acceleration service to foster and support the institutional transformation in Higher Education Institution (HEIs).

Through the organisation of 7 in-person workshops across Europe, the MML approach provided CATALISI implementers with a structured yet adaptable space to connect HEIs around Europe and, where relevant, other societal actors. These workshops enabled participants to share knowledge, experiences, and good practices; to explore how to translate research results into practical use; and to co-reflect and co-create actionable solutions tailored to each institution's transformation pathway.

Specifically, the MML workshops served as an important tool to:

- Deepen and transfer knowledge on the selected topic and intervention area.
- Identify existing good practices and common solutions.
- Explore new scenarios and strategies to advance and consolidate the process of institutional transformation in the organization.

Furthermore, the experience gained through the MML workshops highlighted several critical success factors for mutual learning approaches in order to have a meaningful impact on institutional change:

- A clear definition of institutional priorities and challenges to be addressed.

- The involvement of diverse and relevant stakeholders, both internal and external (if relevant) to universities.
- The use of co-creative tools to foster collaborative problem solving and innovation.
- The presence of a skilled facilitator to ensure meaningful engagement and methodological coherence.
- The customisation of the format and methodology to local needs and institutional contexts, enhancing its relevance and effectiveness.

These elements consistently emerged across the MML workshops as key enablers of success. At the same time, some areas for improvement were identified, including the need to broaden stakeholder diversity (where relevant), increase language flexibility, explore online or hybrid formats to improve accessibility and ensure adequate time, resources, and institutional support for preparation and follow-up activities. These lessons learned are essential not only for improving the MML methodology, but also for embedding mutual learning more systematically within institutional governance structures.

More broadly, the CATALISI experience also reinforces the idea that mutual learning is more than a methodology: it is a strategic orientation for European HEIs operating in an increasingly complex and interconnected landscape. It supports institutions in thinking how to address complex issues such as the adaptation of their internal norms, procedures and cultures to meet the evolving needs of the European Research Area (ERA). In this sense, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning approach developed within the CATALISI project, contributes to the institutional adaptability that is increasingly recognised as crucial for the implementation of the ERA actions and the achievement of long-term transformation goals.

Overall, by fostering a culture of shared learning, collaboration and continuous capacity-building, a mutual learning approach helps universities to face the challenges of modern R&I ecosystems and to co-design responses that are both innovative and inclusive. As such, it should be seen not only as project tools, but as an enduring mechanism to strengthen human capital, promote strategic cooperation and accelerate change across the European Higher Education landscape.

6. REFERENCES

European Commission (2020), *A new ERA for Research and Innovation*, COM(2020) 628 final, Brussels. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628>.

European Commission (2022), Horizon Europe Work programme 2021-2022, *Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area*, DecisionC(2022)2975. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf.

Chakroun M. (2023), *D1.2 – Acting LLs Action Plans*, CATALISI project. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11387363>.

Mentini L. (2023), *D2.1 – Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan*, CATALISI project. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11393609>.

Vilarchao E., Fleck M; Ipolyi I (2022), *Reflection tool for institutional changes in Citizen Science*, TIME4CS project. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7022933>.

APPENDIX A – MML WORKSHOPS' AGENDAS

MML workshop at UJI: *advancing towards responsible research practices in UJI*

19TH JANUARY, UNIVERSITAT JAUME I, 9.30 AM - 2.30 PM, GERMÀ COLÓN ROOM

Universitat Jaume I (UJI), partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>), is organizing this event to share and deepen the knowledge on the evaluation of research ethics in the context of HEIs to advance towards an open and responsible research and innovation system. This event will feature the participation of key internal and external stakeholders and also of CATALISI members. During the event, a series of indicators, focused on the assessment of research projects' performance on gender equality in research and open science, will be discussed. This initiative will allow UJI to evaluate researchers' performance, who are currently participating in research projects, on these intervention areas. This initiative is inspired by *the University Research Responsibility Index* (IRIU) developed by University Miguel Hernández (Elche, Spain).

During the first part of the event, UJI's Adjunct Vice rector of Research and UJI's Vice rector of Social Policies will present the institution's path so far regarding the implementation of research ethics at UJI. A representative from University Miguel Hernández will further share their successful experience in creating a system for the assessment of researchers' good practices. During the second part of the event, participants will be invited to discuss the relevance and suitability of the indicators developed by UJI to assess research project members' performance. These indicators have been previously discussed, in the context of a CATALISI living lab workshop, with key internal and external stakeholders.

- **Session 1** will be devoted to a frontal open exchange on inspirational examples and will have Margarita Vergara (Adjunct Vice rector of Research) and Elsa González Esteban (CATALISI member and Vice rector of Social Policies) as the first speakers. Afterwards, Alberto Campos Pastor, from University Miguel Hernández, will explain how the process of developing their system (IRIU) worked and will present some of their results.
- **Session 2** will be devoted to discussing UJI's proposed indicators and see where improvements can be made. For this, participants (CATALISI Higher Education Universities from across Europe and UJI's stakeholders and researchers) will participate in a co-creation session with the aim to take advantage of the expertise of participants to discuss and share suggestions on the assessment of the indicators.

Language of the
event: English

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
09:30	10:00	Welcome and Introduction to the project	Maria Carmela Fierro (APRE): General Introduction to CATALISI
			Ramón Feenstra (UJI): UJI's transformational goals
			Laura Mentini (APRE): Main questions on the MML methodology
10:00	11:30	<i>Advancing research ethics at UJI: inspirational talks</i>	-Margarita Vergara (Adjunct Vice rector of Research, UJI). <u>Title:</u> "UJI's current challenges on the transformation of research assessment"
			-Elsa González Esteban (CATALISI member and Vice rector of Social Policies, UJI). <u>Title:</u> "Building a deliberative ethical governance for research: ETHNA System"
		<i>The case of University Miguel Hernández: University Research Responsibility Index (IRIU) and the Impact of Research on Sustainable Development Goals (IODS)</i>	-Alberto Campos Pastor (Office of Responsibility in Research, University Miguel Hernández).
11:30	11:45	Open discussion and Questions to speakers	
11:45	12:00	COFFEE BREAK	
12:00	13:55	Co-creation session: <i>Advancing the development of research ethics tools with participants</i>	[APRE and UJI as moderators] Participants: CATALISI members and UJI's internal stakeholders
13:55	14:00	Wrap-up and conclusions	UJI
14:00		NETWORKING LIGHT LUNCH	

15:00

End of the meeting

MML workshop at AUMC: *stimulating responsible conduct of research*

11TH APRIL 2024, 09:00-17:00 AMSTERDAM UMC MEDICAL FACULTY VU ATRIUM (D146)

Amsterdam University Medical Centers (UMC), partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>) is organising a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning event (MML) as part of the project's activities. CATALISI is a 3 years Horizon Europe project that aims to help and support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to successfully implement strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformations in 14 intervention areas through the adoption of acceleration services.

The main goals for Amsterdam UMC in CATALISI are related to improving different aspects of Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) at our institutions, by 1) embedding sustainable education in RCR, and 2) stimulating a positive research culture in various faculties. During this day, we will focus on sharing initiatives and experiences with regards to stimulating Responsible Conduct of Research.

As hosting institution, we will share our knowledge gained in several European projects related to RCR, and share materials developed to stimulate RCR - such as educational materials, and implementation guidelines to improve research culture in institutions. In what way can RCR be stimulated by training? What initiatives to increase research culture exist? Which problems related to RCR and research integrity should be solved in the future - and how? Together with participants, we hope to find some answers to these questions in several co-creation workshop sessions. Participants from universities throughout Europe and beyond will share experiences and knowledge on stimulating RCR. How is for example Research Culture (RC) perceived and defined in different countries? What could be international or local initiatives to improve RC? Answers to these questions can provide valuable insights to further define the CATALISI action plan at university level, and increase our understanding of stimulating RCR in an international context.

Participants at the event are partners from different universities throughout Europe including the CATALISI universities (AUTH, KTU, LUISS, GU, UJI, UCC and APRE as coordinator of the project and facilitator). Participants are also partners from the Erasmus+ project ETHICS (ethics.iliauni.edu.ge), aimed at increasing Responsible Conduct of Research - Research Integrity and Ethics in Georgian Universities. Also, speakers and participants from different levels of our organisations are invited with expertise on research culture and different topics related to RCR and research integrity. Policy makers, researchers and managers are invited to participate, from within and outside Amsterdam UMC and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.

Start time	End time	Description	Presenter
09:30	09:50	Welcome and Introduction to the project CATALISI at Amsterdam University Medical Centers & Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) & the Erasmus ETHICS project	Prof Mariëtte van den Hoven , head of department Ethics, Law and Humanities Dr Miriam van Loon , senior researcher Amsterdam UMC

			Representative APRE
09:50	10:30	Inspiring examples of Stimulating Responsible Conduct of Research	Prof Mariëtte van den Hoven
10:30	11:00	Stimulating a positive Research Culture (SOPS4RI Horizon 2020 project)	Dr Krishma Labib , Research Integrity and Open Science (RIOS) Amsterdam, VU
11:00	11:15	Open discussion and Questions to speakers	All participants
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK	
11:30	11:50	Research Culture policy at the VU	Nathalie Trifkovic , policymaker and Scientific Integrity coordinator VU
11:50	13:00	Co-creation session: parallel workshops on Research Culture [3 groups]	All participants [Amsterdam UMC as moderators]
13:00		NETWORKING LUNCH BUFFET	
14:00	14:15	Concrete examples of RCR training	Amsterdam UMC
14:15	15:40	Interactive poster session on RCR related topics	All Participants [Amsterdam UMC as moderators]
Coffee during poster sessions			
15:45	17:30	Closing lecture: Open Science and Research Integrity	Lex Bouter , Professor emeritus Methodology and Integrity VU, Chair of World Conferences on Research Integrity

MML workshop at Luiss: universities' Third Mission

17th OCTOBER 2024, 9:30-16:00, LUISS GUIDO CARLI, VIALE ROMANIA CAMPUS, ROOM "AULA TOTI"

Luiss Guido Carli, partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>) is organising a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning event (MML) as part of the project's activities. CATALISI is a 3-years Horizon Europe project that aims to help and support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to successfully implement strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformations in 14 intervention areas, through the adoption of acceleration services.

The main goals for Luiss Guido Carli in CATALISI are related to 1) supporting talent circulation and mobility, 2) mainstreaming of open science and digitalisation of research, and 3) public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges. For the MML Luiss has decided to focus on this third intervention area, using the concept of "Third Mission". "Third Mission" encompasses all engagement and communication activities with external stakeholders and society more widely. The specific focus of the MML will be on all "Third Mission" activities connected to research, in particular research valorisation and societal engagement.

As hosting institution, Luiss staff will start the day by giving an overview of the concept of "Third Mission" and by presenting the "Third Mission" work the university has been doing in relation to research, looking at the roles of different teams and entities within the University around this topic.

We will then shift our attention to a number of questions to explore as part of the MML: Does the concept of "Third Mission" exist in all universities? What activities are included under this umbrella term? Which metrics should be used to measure the impact of "Third mission"? How should those be collected? How can these metrics then be incorporated into a university strategy?

Together with participants, key stakeholders and experts, we hope to find some answers to these questions through a co-creation workshop session. Participants will share their experiences and knowledge on the topic, identifying key challenges and possible solutions to adopt. Answers to these questions can provide valuable insights to further define the CATALISI action plan for Luiss institutional transformation and other universities working on the topic. They will also increase Luiss understanding of "Third Mission" and the measurement of research impact in an international context.

All CATALISI universities (AUTH, KTU, GU, UJI, UCC) and APRE, as coordinator of the project and facilitator, will participate to the event. They will be joined by Luiss administrative staff working on "Third Mission" activities at the university. Members of the Luiss faculty who work on "Third Mission" activities related to their research, or have an interest in the topic, will be invited to join as well. The afternoon session, which will revolve around two keynote speeches, will instead be open to the wider public: external participants, in particular APRE associate members - network of the main players in the Italian R&I system, from the academic, scientific, industrial, business and financial worlds - who might have an interest in the topic, will be invited to join online.

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
09:30	10:00	SIGNING OF ATTENDANCE REGISTER	

10:00	10:15	Welcome and Introduction to the project	Representative from Luiss Representative from APRE
10:15	11:15	Presentation of Third Mission activities related to Research carried out by Luiss	Luiss representatives from the Research and Third Mission office, the Library, the Lecture and Seminars office, and the ESG office.
11:15	11:30	COFFEE BREAK	
11:30	13:00	Co-creation session on the measurement of "Third Mission" impact and the inclusion of "Third Mission" metrics in universities' strategies	Luiss, EY and APRE team members as moderators
13:00	14.30	NETWORKING LIGHT LUNCH	
14:30	16:00	2 keynote speeches: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizen Science practices and adoption in universities - Universities contribution in the fight against disinformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maria Rosa Mondardini, Director of Research & Development, Citizen Science Zurich (University of Zurich and ETH Zurich) - Gianni Riotta, Director, Data Lab (Luiss)
16:00	End of meeting		

MML workshop at UCC: improving research culture: financial sustainability in research

14th NOVEMBER 2024, 09:00 – 13:30, UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK

University College Cork partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>) is organising this event with the aim to exchange experience and knowledge amongst implementers on the topic of **'Improving Research Culture: Financial Sustainability in Research'**.

Research performing organisations operate in diverse organisational and regional operational and policy contexts. Institutional decision making across the ERA could benefit from wider sharing of experience and good practice around these diverse contexts and better understand the variety of financial systems, models and mechanisms that are employed and applied.

Mutual learning on these financial logics, strategies and tactics that are embedded in our research systems is critical if we are to future proof the research eco-system and support a resilient and enabling environment for high quality and responsible science.

This topic is core to application of CATALISI acceleration services for transformation in UCC and is at the heart of our living lab intervention area and wider action plan. A brief background reading document is provided, outlining some key dimensions of the topic as identified in our own local context.

Employing a Mutual Learning methodology the session will enable structured dialogue to generate critical dialogue around the topic of Financial Sustainability in Research. It will convene expertise from a European, Irish national and UCC local institutional context and seek to co-examine:

1. The Policy Landscape and Current State for Financially Sustaining Quality Research
2. The diverse finance and funding models and mechanisms that underpin our research systems: good practice, risks and opportunities
3. The impacts of key drivers and intersecting issues that are transforming Research Cultures – particularly Open Science and Societal Partnerships

This session will contribute to deepening mutual understanding across diverse perspectives around the issues and shed light on how we might refine or devise interventions that can be advanced through CATALISI.

Inviting a critical peer interrogation of UCC intervention area and activities, an anticipated outcome is the identification of potential follow up opportunities to enhance the effectiveness and impact-making efforts of local action plans and overall exploitation of CATALISI acceleration services.

A rapporteur will be in attendance to record discussions on the day and the UCC team will produce a Mutual Learning Key Insights Report as output.

Abstract

The CATALISI MML Event organized by University College Cork will concentrate on the topic of Improving Research Culture: Financial Sustainability in Research. For this purpose, the event will be divided into two parts.

Part 1 of the session is devoted to informative exchange to Co-explore the Policy Landscape and Context Conditions for Financial Sustainability for Research from a European, national (Irish) and then, finally, local/institutional (UCC) level. These three areas of analysis will be examined by, respectively:

- Enora Bennetot Pruvot, Deputy Director Governance, Funding & Public Policy Development at European University Association,
- Lisa Keating, Director of Research and Innovation, Irish Universities Association,
- Dr. David O'Connell, Director of Research Support and Policy at University College Cork

Part 2 is dedicated to **Co-creating new insights for transformation** - to inform pathways for the implementation of institutional changes. The session will introduce and invite critical peer interrogation of UCC intervention area and activities, through this dialogue, we will critically examine and co-develop mutual learning around financial systems, models and mechanisms for enabling a financially sustainable research system that supports rich and diverse research community and activity at all levels.

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
09:00 (GMT)	09:20	Welcome and Introductions	UCC and APRE Representative
PART 1 - Co-exploring the Policy Landscape and Context Conditions			
09:20	09:40	A European Perspective <i>EUA Survey on Financial Sustainability – Emerging learnings and Insights with respect to Research Mission of institutions and Financial Sustainability of Research</i>	Enora Bennetot Pruvot <i>Deputy Director Governance, Funding & Public Policy Development at European University Association</i>
09:40	10:00	An Irish Perspective	Lisa Keating <i>Director of Research and Innovation, Irish Universities Association</i>
10:00	10:15	An Institutional Perspective	David O'Connell
10:15	10:30	COFFEE BREAK	
PART 2 – Co-Creating New Insights for Transformation			

10:30	10:45	Introduction to UCC intervention area and activities	David Hogan
10:45	12:15	Mutual learning workshop Critical peer interrogation of pathways for implementing institutional change	Facilitated Discussion moderated by Martin Galvin
12:15	12:30	WRAP AND CLOSE	
12:30	13:30	LUNCH AND NETWORKING	
13:30	END OF EVENT		

MML workshop at KTU: *Participatory Research Practices at KTU: Infrastructure and Strategic Guideline*

12th DECEMBER 2024, 10:00 – 15:00, KTU

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>) is organising MML event with the aim to exchange experiences and knowledge on the intervention area “Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges” and transformational pathways towards open science, integrity in research and participatory research practices.

In this intervention area KTU is focusing on a challenge/question: How to enhance public engagement and inclusion of stakeholders, to solve societal challenges? Our long-term vision is to be a university implementing social change and cooperating with society. The medium-long goal is by the end of the project to achieve the increase in awareness of the university academic and research staff of the benefits of public engagement in research. Short-term goal is to enact citizen science hub.

The MML event “*Participatory Research Practices at KTU: Infrastructure and Strategic Guidelines*” focuses on introducing and exploring the growing role of citizen science in research, particularly in the context of Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) and its broader academic community. The event aims to discuss infrastructure, strategic guidelines, and real-world applications of citizen science projects across different fields.

Addressing the agenda of the event, expected outputs and outcomes of the MML event focus on:

1. Introducing Citizen Science Guidelines at KTU:

- presentation of the official guidelines for implementing citizen science projects at KTU. This provides the foundation for understanding how the university plans to engage the public in scientific research. The focus is on setting standards for quality, ethics, and collaboration in citizen science.

2. Activities of Citizen Science Hub:

- introduction the hub's role at KTU. This includes explaining the structure and goals of the hub, how it serves as a center for coordinating citizen science projects, and its role in fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The hub acts as a resource for students, researchers, and the general public interested in participating in or organizing citizen science initiatives.

3. Practices from Social Citizen Science Projects (TIME4CS, YouCount, LibOCS):

- experiences of specific citizen science projects that focus on social issues. The projects mentioned—TIME4CS, YouCount, and LibOCS— acts as case studies illustrating how citizen science can address pressing social challenges and how citizen science activities might be fostered at the universities and libraries.

4. Citizen Science Projects in Architecture and Other Disciplines

- discussion on how citizen science is being applied in architecture and possibly other fields, highlighting innovative approaches where the public helps gather data, provide insights, or even co-create solutions. These projects explore urban planning and environmental design.

5. Co-creation session:

After the presentations, there is an interactive discussion session. This segment is organized as World Cafe and allows attendees to ask questions, provide feedback, and share their experiences. The co-creation session covers all 3 intervention areas at KTU.

Overall Focus: The event will emphasize how participatory research practices, especially citizen science, can contribute to more inclusive, diverse, and impactful research practices. By involving the public in scientific discovery, the event aligns with the goal of democratizing knowledge and empowering individuals from different backgrounds to engage in research that has direct societal implications.

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
09:30	10:00	Welcome and Introduction to the project	Representative from host HEI, Egle Butkeviciene Representative from APRE, Laura Mentini
10:00	12:00	Participatory Research Practices at KTU: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing Citizen Science Guidelines at KTU • Activities of Citizen Science Hub • Social Citizen science projects (TIME4CS, YouCount, LibOCS) • Citizen science projects in architecture and other disciplines 	Renata Visinskaite, manager of R&I projects Egle Butkeviciene, Head of Citizen Science Hub Gintare Tautkeviciene, Director of the KTU Library Kestutis Zaleckis, Chief project researcher
12:00	13:00	Lunch	
13:00	14:30	Co-creation session: Sharing experience on organizing participatory research and talent mobility	All
14:30	16:00	Visit to Campus Library, M-Lab, KTU Infinity Lab. Discussion on <i>Spaces for Co-Creation</i>	
16:00	End of meeting		

MML workshop at AUTH: *integrating open citizen science in universities: building stakeholder engagement and Living Lab ecosystems*

22nd JANUARY 2025, 09:30-16:00, ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY RESEARCH DISSEMINATION CENTER (KEDEA)

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) is hosting a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) event as part of the Horizon Europe project **CATALISI** (<https://catalisi.eu/>). This event aims to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among participants to advance the integration of Open Science and Citizen Science principles and practices within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).

CATALISI is a three-year Horizon Europe project designed to support HEIs in implementing strategies for institutional transformation across 14 intervention areas through tailored acceleration services. As part of this mission, the MML at AUTH will explore how Open Science and Citizen Science practices can be adopted and further developed to enhance awareness, engagement, and societal impact.

The MML will begin with an overview of AUTH's efforts to embed Open and Citizen Science principles into its institutional strategies. Participants will engage in discussions about key challenges and opportunities, addressing critical questions such as:

- How can Open Science and Citizen Science be effectively integrated into university structures?
- What steps can universities take to enhance societal engagement?

A key part of the event will be a co-creation workshop, where participants—academics, experts, and stakeholders—will collaborate to identify challenges and propose solutions for integrating Open and Citizen Science into institutional strategies. This session will provide valuable insights to inform AUTH's action plan and contribute to the broader goals of the CATALISI project.

The event will also feature a showcase by Thess-AHALL, demonstrating how Living Labs can effectively engage communities and researchers to co-create solutions for healthcare challenges. Contributions from CATALISI partners, including KTU, GU, UJI, UCC, and APRE, the project coordinator, will enrich the discussions, fostering an exchange of best practices and innovative ideas.

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
9:30	10:30	Guided Tour of AUTH's Library , led by Lia Ollandezou, Coordinator of the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link.	
10:30	11:00	Arrival at Aristotle University Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA)	
11:00	11:30	Welcome and Introduction to the project AUTH's Journey – Transformational Pathways	Laura Mentini Stefania Laneve, Project Managers at APRE Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, Director of the Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab, AUTH

11:30	13:00	<p>Integrating Open Science & Citizen Science in Universities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations: Challenges and Opportunities for Embedding Open and Citizen Science in University Structures, with insights from the Hellenic Open Science Initiative and examples of integration in Greek universities. <p><i>This session will showcase practical strategies, highlight barriers, and explore opportunities for enhancing transparency, collaboration, and societal engagement in higher education.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, Lab of Medical Informatics Medical School, AUTH • Lia Ollandezou, Library and Information Center, Coordinator of Hellenic Academic Libraries Link • Prof. Alexander Chatzigeorgiou, Department of applied Informatics, University of Macedonia
13:00	13:45	Open discussion and Q&A Session	
13:45	14:45	NETWORKING LIGHT LUNCH	
14:45	16:00	<p>Co-creation session: Exploring Pathways for Open and Citizen Science Integration in University Ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants will work in small groups to develop actionable strategies for integrating Open and Citizen Science into AUTH's institutional framework, focusing on data management, sharing, and collaboration. These solutions will inform AUTH's action plan for Open Science integration. 	
16:00	17:00	<p>Engaging Communities Through Living Labs: Thess-AHALL Showcase</p> <p>Demonstrating how Thess-AHALL engages citizens and researchers to address healthcare challenges through co-creation.</p>	Thess-AHALL Representatives
17:00	End of meeting		

MML workshop at UG: societal engagement in Higher Education: building stakeholders cooperation and reaching out to external partners

11TH APRIL 2025, 08:30-15:30, UNIVERSITY OF GDANSK, FACULTY OF ECONOMICS (SOPOT) AND MAIN CAMPUS (GDANSK-PRZYMORZE)

University of Gdansk (UG) is hosting a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) event as part of the Horizon Europe project **CATALISI** (<https://catalisi.eu/>). CATALISI is a three-year Horizon Europe project designed to support HEIs in implementing strategies for institutional transformation across 14 intervention areas through tailored acceleration services.

This event aims to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among participants to advance the cooperation between universities and society, knowledge transfer, and engagement of external partners. The lessons learned and resulting good practices will be spread within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) engaged in the CATALISI project. As a result, HEIs involved will be able to showcase and disseminate results to the broader audience.

The MML will begin with an overview of UG's practices in engaging, supporting, and maintaining ties with different types of external stakeholders (teachers and students of secondary schools, business partners and business organizations). Special attention will be given to the university's third mission and its role in providing education and knowledge transfer to society through channels other than simple offer of study programs. Participants will engage in discussions about key challenges and opportunities, addressing critical questions such as:

- What are the most efficient practices in Societal Engagement?
- How can knowledge be disseminated beyond simply offering study programs?
- Which actors should be engaged?
- How can universities meet society's expectations in carrying out third mission?
- What are the expected benefits to society and the university?
- How to activate business support while carrying out the third mission?

The MML will include not only workshops and discussions but also a "participating observation". During the date of MML UG will be hosting the finals of the *Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad*, which is a competition organized by UG and directed at high schools. The MML participants will be able to witness (and ask questions) at different stages of the parallel event.

This will provide a ground for a co-creation workshop, where participants—academics, experts, and stakeholders—will collaborate to identify challenges for promoting, organizing, and carrying out university extra-educational activities. Also, potential solutions can be discussed. This workshop will be continued after all MML-related meetings to set up a list of solutions assigned to challenges they should help to face.

We hope that this session will help UG improve strategies of society engagement and at the same time, other participants will be able to take home some of the best practices identified.

Start time	End time	Room	Item description	Presenter	Possible online streaming
08.30	08.55	C201	Welcome coffee		
08.55	09.05	C209	Introduction to CATALISI project	Stefania Laneve, APRE	YES
09.05	09.30	C209	Societal engagement for HEIs. Showcasing best practices and solutions <i>This session will showcase practical strategies, highlight barriers, and explore opportunities for societal engagement</i>	Vice-Dean Magdalena Markiewicz	YES
09.30	10.00	C209	Case study – Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad This session will show all the steps needed in organizing big-scale (country reach) event with more than a hundred external stakeholders. What are the critical success factors and what are main risks.	Przemysław Borkowski	YES
10.00	10.45	Aula	Participatory observation in large-scale event <i>(our group will be visiting the main Olympiad competition event and accompanying activities e.g. workshops for teachers, laboratory presentation, etc. thus being able to collect first-hand experience)</i>	Przemysław Borkowski	NO
10.45	11.00	C201	Discussion over coffee		
11.00	12:00	C209	Co-creation workshop part 1 <i>Exploring ways to better cooperate with different external stakeholders.</i> <i>The whole group will be divided into subgroups working on different groups of stakeholders (companies, public agencies, local authorities, schools, NGOs...)</i> <i>Part 1 – screening the barriers</i>	Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz	YES
12.00	13.00	Can-teen	NETWORKING LUNCH		
13.00	13.40	C303	Engaging business stakeholders	Dariusz Tłoczyński +	YES

			<i>How to maintain business ties and ensure business support of different university activities</i>	business representatives	
13.40	14.30	Aula	Participatory observation <i>join the Olympiad event to witness the final prize awards</i>	Przemysław Borkowski	NO
14.30	15.30	C209	Co-creation workshop part 2 <i>Exploring ways to better cooperate with different external stakeholders (secondary schools, ministry of education/science, business). Part 2 - update of list of barriers Working on solutions and tools</i>	Agnieszka Szmelter-Jarosz	YES
15:30			END OF THE MEETING		
18.30	SOCIAL DINNER				

APPENDIX B – MML WORKSHOPS' REPORTS

UJI MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	MOBILISATION AND MUTUAL LEARNING EVENT: ADVANCING TOWARDS RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH PRACTICES IN UJI
Date	19 th January
Venue	Germà Colón room, Universitat Jaume I
Length	From 9.30 am to 2.30pm (5H)
Total number of participants	25

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: Universitat Jaume I (UJI)

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	22	Vice-Rector	2
		Middle Management	1
		Technical staff	3
		Researcher	16
Research and Technology Organisation			
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or			

Innovation Agency			
Civil Society Organisation	3	Project Manager	3
Industry			
Other			

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)	The aim of the event was to share and deepen the knowledge on the evaluation of research ethics in the context of HEIs in order to advance towards an open and responsible research and innovation system. Specifically, the main goals were, on the one hand, to explain the work that has been done at UJI regarding responsible research practices and research integrity and also present inspiring initiatives from other universities. On the other hand, discuss with the participants the ways in which UJI can promote a scale of indicators to measure performance on Open Access (OA) and also how to promote a more active involvement of UJI's ethics committee with researchers.
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	The main topics of the session were: UJI's structural transformations on research ethics and integrity implemented so far as well as the work done at other institutions (Universidad Miguel Hernández) that might be inspiring for UJI's goals. On the other hand, possible actions to address and promote transformations on OA and to enhance the ethics committee performance were discussed.
Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	The main challenges addressed were: how to promote and raise awareness about the relevance of OA among the research community; the effectiveness of awards or any other acknowledgements to promote good practices on OA; specific challenges on the promotion of OA; the way ethics committees work on other institutions; how communication between ethics committees and researchers can be promoted and improved; how to report misconduct in research

	practices; how to address the expansion of Artificial Intelligence and its challenges regarding research ethics.
<p>Activities performed <i>(Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</i></p>	<p>On the first part of the event, three speakers shared their experience improving research assessment and research ethics structures in Spanish universities. First, Margarita Vergara (adjunct Vice-rector of Research at UJI) explained the work done at UJI regarding the transformation of research assessment criteria and also the upcoming challenges. Second, Elsa González Esteban (Vice-rector of Social Policies and Catalisi member) shared the work done in the framework of the ETHNA System project, where a set of tools for RRI were developed: an ethical code of good practices in research, an ethics committee, an ethical hotline and process indicators to report. Last, Alberto Campos Pastor, from Miguel Hernández University (UMH), explained their experience implementing IRIU, a system to measure researchers' adherence to the UMH guidelines for responsibility in research and also with the Sustainable Development Goals.</p> <p>On the second part of the event, there was a co-creation session (group discussion) with the rest of the participants dedicated to advancing in the development of research ethics tools. During this session, moderated by Ramón Feenstra and Laura Bernal, Catalisi members and also UJI researchers and technical staff discussed the potential and also the obstacles for the implementation of a scale to measure researchers' performance on OA and how to improve the work of the UJI ethics committee.</p>

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

During this MML we were able to address all the topics we planned to discuss. In the first part of the session, UJI's work so far on responsible research practices was presented along with some inspiring initiatives from other institutions. This, together with the presentations and the moderation provided by UJI Catalisi members during the second part, helped participants understand the context where UJI will be applying transformational changes. This way, the dynamic was very useful for the discussion on how to develop specific actions to promote transformations on OA and to enhance the ethics committee performance. We were able to gather very interesting ideas and proposals as a result of this exchange that will be later discussed more extensively among UJI team members and stakeholders.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

The participants rated this event from 1 to 5 (1 being the lowest and 5 the highest score) in a follow-up survey that addressed the following topics: 1) the tools and information provided (score: 4-5); 2) the explanation of the methodology (score: 4-5); 3) the communication of the event (score: 4-5); 4) the place and the equipment for the event (score: 3-5); 5) the timing and duration of the event (score: 3-5); 6) the materials provided at the event (score: 4-5); 7) the rhythm and development of the workshop (score: 4-5); 8) the structure of the workshop (score: 4-5); 9) the level of interaction during the workshop (score: 4-5); 10) the performance of the activities in promoting teamwork and collaboration among participants (score: 3-5); 11) the opportunity to share insights (score: 5); 12) if the workshop gave them new ideas (score: 3.5); 13) if the workshop enabled them to think more broadly (score: 4-5); 14) if the workshop met the expectations (score_ 4-5). Also, in the open questions, participants answered that they would recommend this type of workshop (presentations and then group discussions) and the majority also said they considered this workshop to be replicable at their institution. Finally, participants added some suggestions, such as circulating the questions in advance, to improve the dynamic.

The event was rated very positively by the participants, with only two topics being scored lower than 4 and only suggestions being made regarding the materials. Also, the question about the opportunity to share insights was rated with the maximum score by all the participants who answered the survey.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (max. 500 words)

We positively value the use of the MML methodology. It was very useful and provided helpful tools to exchange ideas and share knowledge among the participants. It enabled and facilitated the goal of the workshop, which was to explain UJI's needs for transformation and then generate a discussion around specific areas that are going to be targeted at UJI during Catalisi. However, it might be useful if the methodology was more easily adaptable to the specific needs of the institution and to the type and number of participants of the event.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? *(max. 300 words)*

Regarding the first topic, the promotion of Open Science at UJI, some questions such as the need for economic support to make structural changes or the need for a cultural change (creating awareness among researchers of the relevance of Open Science) were addressed. More specifically, participants suggested creating a label (OA champion) or promoting role models and PhD teaming in spreading good practices in OA. Regarding the work of the ethics committee, it was suggested to implement fines or a system for reporting people who violate research integrity or to create a platform for complaints. Also, it was considered helpful for researchers to be able to see the state of the process of going through the ethics committee.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. *(max. 150 words)*

The insights gathered during the MML will be used to improve the action plans for some of the intervention areas targeted by UJI. Those intervention areas will be: Open Science and Research assessment (ethics committees). This way, during the MML, specific actions for UJI's institutional transformation were discussed, such as the creation of a set of indicators to measure researchers' compliance with OA policies, ways for raising awareness among the research community about the relevance of Open Science and the improvement of the way UJI's ethics committee works (communication, following up projects, the risks of Artificial Intelligence). The suggestions made by the participants (included in the answer above) will be discussed by the UJI team and considered for their implementation.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. *(max. 300 words)*

As it was explained in the answer above, the MML was useful to target specific questions concerning the design of UJI's actions towards institutional transformation regarding the promotion of Open Science and the improvement of the performance of the ethics committee. It helped clarify some topics (such as tools for raising awareness on Open Science, improving communication between the ethics committee and researchers) that are key in achieving our goals for the transformational pathway.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? *(max. 300 words)*

UJI's top management has been involved in Catalisi since the beginning of the project. Elsa González Esteban (UJI team) currently occupies the vice-rectorate of social policies. Also, other vice-rectors (Vice-Rector of Research, Vice-Rector of Innovation and Dissemination) have been acting as internal stakeholders from the beginning of the project. Their collaboration has been key to set realistic and suitable goals and also in the design of the actions (providing their support and advice on what's achievable) that will be implemented to meet our goals for institutional transformation.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

Following this event, UJI will continue designing and planning strategies to promote Open Science among researchers and also enhancing the performance of the ethics committee (which were the topics addressed during the co-creation session of the MML). To achieve these goals, UJI Catalisi team will work in collaboration with OCIT (UJI's Office for Cooperation in Research and Technological Development), UJI's library and some top management (Vice-rectorate of Research, Vice-rectorate of Innovation and Dissemination). This way, we will focus on creating a small group of people to define UJI's indicators for measuring researchers' compliance with Open Science policies and to analyse similar initiatives developed by other institutions. Also, we will work with some people from OCIT (Laura Bernal, also part of the Catalisi team) to improve the performance of the ethics committee.

Also, it is worth noting that on February 12th, UJI Catalisi members submitted an action plan to the Vice-rectorate of research targeting institutional transformation in the area of academic assessment and open access.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

Yes, it was our first experience using this methodology. It might be useful to apply it again in a context where group discussions are needed to gather ideas for institutional changes. So it is likely this methodology will be used again at UJI.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

We think it might be useful to make the necessary changes on the methodology so it is more easily adaptable to each institution needs and goals. From our side, maybe next time it would be useful to find a room more suited to promote teamwork.

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on the CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

AUMC MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Event: Stimulating Responsible conduct of research
Date	April 11 th , 2024
Venue	Amsterdam UMC medical faculty VU
Length	09:00-17:30
Total number of participants	+ - 70

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: Amsterdam University Medical Centers

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	70 approx.	Rector	1
		Vice-Rector	1
		General Manager	2
		Researchers/professors	65
		Administrative	1
Research and Technology Organisation			
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency			
Civil Society Organisation			

Industry			
Other			

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)	Sharing initiatives and experiences with regards to stimulating Responsible Conduct of Research and stimulating a positive research culture.
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	Main topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible conduct of research - Research culture
Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	The main goals for Amsterdam UMC in CATALISI are related to improving different aspects of Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) at our institutions, by 1) embedding sustainable education in RCR, and 2) stimulating a positive research culture in various faculties.
Activities performed (<i>Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words</i>)	<p>The event started with several presentations to share our knowledge gained in several European projects related to RCR, and share materials developed to stimulate RCR</p> <p>During the MML event, we held co-creation sessions in which participants shared their experience and knowledge on stimulating responsible conduct of research. During this workshop, 70 international researchers, with an expertise in the field of research ethics, participated. Every participant was asked to answer the following three questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What would be a metaphor to describe research culture? 2. What would be possible solutions to stimulate a positive research culture? 3. Who should be responsible for this change in research culture? <p>To facilitate a discussion, we divided the four group into four groups. For each question, participants first</p>

	<p>had to write down their ideas on post-its. Subsequently, there was a group discussion in which the answers written down on the post-its were discussed.</p> <p>After this workshop, we had interactive poster sessions on different topics regarding responsible conduct of research (e.g. open science, RIOS, etc.)</p>
--	---

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

For the workshop, we wanted to experiment with the use of metaphors to describe research culture as a means to define research culture and make it discussable. It was interesting to see that so many participants came up with different metaphors, which worked out better than we had expected. Additionally, this led to fruitful discussions among the participants. Moreover, participants came up with good ideas for improving research culture, which we could incorporate into (policy) proposals.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

Overall, participants found the workshop to be interactive, informative and interesting. They found the workshop on research culture and the interactive poster sessions insightful and useful. The main take away message was that there are many different tools to improve research culture and responsible conduct of research, and that we should take the next step in carrying out these tools in practice.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (*max. 500 words*)

The combination of some topical lectures by experts in the field, with interactive sessions where people can exchange ideas and insights was valuable for us and the participants to gain more knowledge on the topic or research culture and responsible conduct of research.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

Participants came up with several metaphors to describe research culture, but the overall connotation of current research culture was negative. To improve research culture, we should focus on the following key principles:

1. Recognize and reward researchers beyond the scope of the current academic reward system
2. Promote openness and transparency (eg by publishing failure cases, organizing meetings/forums to discuss cases with other researchers)
3. Provide more extensive and more tailored training for researchers (on ethics, supervision, development, etc.)
4. Flatten the hierarchy in research departments
5. Encourage young researchers (by recognizing & rewarding, better mentorship)
6. Improve structural and policy measures
7. Promote freedom of research

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

The insights we have received during this event will be used to write an exploratory article on the use of metaphors in research culture, and international ideas on how to improve RC.

Building on this workshop, we will conduct a qualitative study, as part of the CATALISI project within our own institution, to further investigate the meaning of research culture for researchers in different departments at the University ("Vrije Universiteit) and University Medical Center of Amsterdam.

Furthermore, the key principles that the participants have identified to foster a positive research culture will be taken into account in prospective trainings and policymaking.

We also received interest in the trainings we develop related to RCR and will share our knowledge with other HEIs.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

Through this event, we have gained valuable insights to further define the CATALISI action plan at university level and increase our understanding of stimulating responsible conduct of research in an international context. Because participants came from different universities across Europe, we were able to gather opinions and ideas from many different perspectives.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

Yes, for example our policymaker on Research Integrity and RI training were involved, and were engaged in the topic. We involved them in the program and they have good insights on the goals for transformation we have. This event and other meetings help to define share goals with regards to improving RCR in our institution.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

The MML workshop included a try-out for the qualitative study that we are aiming to conduct. In this qualitative study, we will investigate the perspective and definition of different research across various departments in the University/University Medical Center. In addition, likewise as in the MML workshop, we will investigate their needs with regard to stimulating a positive research culture.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

In other conferences and workshops we use the same type of set-up, including informational lectures, as well as interactive sessions.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

Participants had no improvements for the workshop.
Recommendation would be to make sure the MML is interactive.

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

LUISS MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	Mobilization and Mutual Learning Event: Universities' Third Mission
Date	17 October 2024
Venue	Luiss Campus at Viale Romania 32, Rome
Length	1 day Event
Total number of participants	33 Participants

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: Luiss University

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	27	Professors	4
		Researchers	1
		Researcher support roles	4
		Administrative Staff	18
Research and Technology Organisation		Project Managers	3
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency			
Civil Society Organisation			

Industry			
Other		Consultants	3

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

<p>Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)</p>	<p>The aim of the MML event was to collectively explore the concept of the Third Mission and the activities associated with it, particularly in relation to research. The objective at Luiss was specified as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A moment for direct comparison with other European universities, to share reciprocal experiences and demonstrate our role as joint actors towards change. 2) A moment for comparison with our colleagues, to improve dialogue and best practices.
<p>Summary of the main topic(s) covered (<i>max. 500 words</i>)</p>	<p>The specific focus of the MML Event was on all “Third Mission” activities connected to research, in particular research valorisation and societal engagement.</p> <p>Giving an overview of the concept of “Third Mission”, Luiss presented the “Third Mission” work the university has been doing in relation to research, looking at the roles of different teams and entities within the University around the topic.</p> <p>With the initial brainstorming session, the concept of “Third Mission” was analyzed and explored.</p> <p>In the participatory sessions, the topics of communication of research, commissioned engaged research and public engagement projects and events were addressed.</p>
<p>Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (<i>max. 500 words</i>)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing the number of participants involved in “Third Mission” activities and keeping the numerical core of involvement constant; - Alignment of activities among the Offices of the same Institution and among different

	<p>Universities, in order to create a compact action aimed at institutional change;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperation among Universities members and Business Partners in order to outline a common strategy; - Identifying the right parameters to investigate in the monitoring surveys, in order to measure the impact of the "Third Mission" in the short-medium-long term and know how to identify the next strategic steps; - Have the appropriate number of human resources involved in "Third Mission" activities, suitable and sustainable physical facilities, adequate infrastructure.
<p>Activities performed <i>(Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentations of the Third Mission activities related to Research carried out by Luiss; - Alphabet ice-breaking activity, where participants – divided into 3 groups – were asked to think about one concept related to "Third Mission" for each letter of the Alphabet, with the aim of creating a shared vocabulary; - Incremental knowledge activity, where participant – divided into 3 groups – were asked to discuss 3 aspects (Measurement of Impact, Collection of Measurements and Challenges to collection) in relation to the 3 most important concepts related to "Third Mission" (Communication of Research, Commissioned Engaged Research and Public Engagement Project and Events). - Feedback of the knowledge activity, where a member of each group was asked to present the main points that have been added to the board, to help the following group to progress with the work in the next round, explaining the most relevant elements that emerged from the collective analysis.

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

Reflecting on the meaning of the "Third Mission" within universities and **sharing best practices** to facilitate its activities, as well as **measuring its impact**, was the goal of the event. The presentations on the "Third Mission" activities carried out by the various LUISS offices, the exploratory brainstorming on the language of the "Third Mission", and the sessions involving all participants allowed for a conceptual deepening of the term. Starting from a common vocabulary, it was also possible to investigate the procedures that can be implemented in view of institutional change. In this sense, **the main objective of the event was achieved, and the event can be considered a success.**

As evidence of this, the awarding of a very positive score (**4,64/5**) to the event by the participants shows that the **goal of the event was fulfilled.**

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

Going to further elaborate on the previous question, based on the totality of responses to the feedback survey aimed at evaluating the workshop and its various components (clarity and understandability of the presentations given; communication of the event; place and equipment for the event; duration of the event; materials provided at the event; rhythm and development of the workshop; structure of the workshop; level of participation and collaboration during the workshop; opportunity to share your insights during the workshop) **using a scale from 0 to 5 points, the weighted average is 4.64 points, which indicates that the organization of the event in general can be considered a success.**

In particular, the timing, duration, location, and pace of the event received very positive scores (**4.9 or 5/5**), followed by the clarity of the presentations, the methodology used in the workshop, the structure of the workshop, and the level of participant interaction in the activities (**4.75/5**). Finally, collaboration among participants, the ease of sharing ideas during the workshop, the provided materials, the achievement of new ideas, and deeper thinking were rated positively (**ranging from 4.16 to 4.63/5**).

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (*max. 500 words*)

We consider the proposed methodology (MML workshop) very useful, as it represents a true moment of sharing within a formal context.

Through presentations and the active participation of various university departments, we were able to illustrate how the "Third Mission" is structured at LUISS, which offices are involved, and how we carry out the related research activities. This moment, in addition to allowing for the presentation of the University's functioning externally, was valuable in **strengthening the sense of cohesion and unity among members of the same institution.**

Through activities aimed at creating an atmosphere of cooperation and sincere exchange (brainstorming and group work), we were able to compare and measure the experiences of other universities regarding the "Third Mission," **gaining interesting**

insights on elements to implement and learning from others' paths about aspects to focus on (for example, the use of a particular repository for librarians to sustain Open Access Publications and the evaluation of the transition level towards this goal).

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

From the event, and in particular from the shared sessions, it emerged that **the participants involved have a good awareness of the "engagement"** that a university institution seeks to achieve. In this sense, the testimonies of the participants (both in the participatory sessions and in the feedback survey) repeatedly confirmed their understanding of the concept of the Third Mission and a certain awareness of the need to share ideas, engage people and stakeholders outside the institution, and monitor the scope of engagement activities. They also recognized the difficulty of always obtaining reliable quantitative measurements.

Along this trajectory, continuing with events of this type but with a more targeted approach would help further in the implementation of practices that facilitate institutional change.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

The insights received during the event will be used to build an **impact assessment framework for Third Mission activities**, which will be integrated into the broader university strategy. By **incorporating specific KPIs, the framework will help monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of Third Mission initiatives**, particularly in areas like **research valorisation and societal engagement**. The event's discussions on metrics, challenges, and solutions will directly inform this process, enhancing the university's strategic approach. The insights will contribute to refining future actions related to Open Science and Public Engagement, ensuring alignment with Luiss's long-term goals and international debates on Third Mission.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

We consider that the event was highly useful for the advancement of our transformational pathway, as it provided an opportunity to engage in meaningful dialogue about the concept of "Third Mission" and its connection to research impact and societal engagement. By **exploring key questions around the measurement of impact and the inclusion of "Third Mission" metrics in university strategies, we gained valuable insights into both the challenges and best practices that can inform our institutional transformation**. The co-creation workshop fostered collaborative problem-solving, where participants shared experiences and identified solutions to address challenges related to data collection, sustainability, and stakeholder engagement. Additionally, the keynote speeches highlighted relevant practices in citizen science and the role of universities in combating disinformation, further aligning with Luiss's strategic vision of enhancing its social impact. **Through discussions on public engagement projects and commissioned research, we identified the need for a more integrated approach, involving cross-departmental collaboration and the**

proper use of tools like AI to measure impact. This event, by refining our understanding of these topics and offering a platform for knowledge exchange, provided practical inputs to strengthen our "Third Mission" initiatives and guide future strategic decisions.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

We consider that involvement of top-level managers in the event would significantly contribute to accelerating the transformation in the areas discussed, particularly concerning the Third Mission. **Having senior leadership present would help elevate the importance of this theme within the right institutional settings, ensuring that it is taken seriously at the highest levels of decision-making.** Top-level managers have the authority and influence to drive systemic change and would be in a position to align the strategies discussed with broader institutional goals. Their presence would also provide greater leverage for steering university practices in the right direction, especially when it comes to integrating research and societal impact in a more structured way.

Additionally, **these managers can help guide political support for institutional changes, ensuring that the necessary resources, policies, and support structures are in place to sustain the transformation.** By being actively involved, **senior leaders can bridge the gap between academic departments, external stakeholders, and policy-making, making sure that the Third Mission is not just a theoretical concept but a tangible part of the university's long-term strategy.** This top-down support would significantly enhance the capacity for meaningful change and help universities respond to emerging societal needs.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

The follow-up of this event will **involve meetings with internal stakeholders to further advance the work on the Third Mission strategy. These discussions will focus on integrating the insights gained into the development of an impact assessment framework, using specific KPIs to monitor and evaluate Third Mission activities.** By engaging relevant university teams, we will ensure that the framework aligns with the broader university strategy and supports ongoing initiatives in research valorisation and societal engagement. These internal meetings will help refine the approach and facilitate the successful implementation of the university's Third Mission objectives.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

It was the first time used this methodology for the exchange of opinions and experiences, and it was very formative. As highlighted in the feedback survey, **several participants expressed interest in applying this method to other administrative, educational, and communicative contexts.** We therefore believe that we can certainly use it, applying it to new events and topics.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

Based on the feedback and our experience from this MML event, several recommendations can be made to improve future sessions.

1. **Provide More Information Material:** It would be beneficial to offer more materials both before and after the workshop. For example, sharing the presentation used during the event or sending a summary of the workshop results via email would enhance participants' understanding and allow them to refer back to key points.
2. **Revise Presentation Formats:** The presentations could be restructured to be more dynamic and informal. Rather than brief 10-minute presentations from each office, we could encourage more interactive sessions that allow for genuine exchanges of ideas, similar to the format used on the second day of the event. This would foster greater engagement and dialogue among participants.
3. **Enhance Tools for Collaboration:** While the use of a digital/interactive whiteboard was noted as a helpful tool, the cost implications should be considered. However, improving such tools for clearer writing could make the event more visually engaging and facilitate better interaction during collaborative sessions.
4. **Encourage Networking and Location Exchange:** Facilitating the exchange of location-based experiences among participants could provide valuable insights into other external organizations. This would offer an opportunity to learn from diverse contexts and strengthen the overall network.

By implementing these suggestions, future MMLs can further improve Participant Engagement, Knowledge Sharing, and Networking Opportunities.

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

UCC MML WORKSHOP REPORT

7. General Information

Event Title	UCC-CATALISI MML Event
Date	Thursday 14 November 09:00 – 13:30 (GMT)
Venue	University College Cork Campus
Length	4.5 hours
Total number of participants	15

8. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: University College Cork (UCC)

9. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	12	Professional Staff Planning/Public Engagement	2
		Office of Vice-President in Research and Innovation	3
		Researchers/Pis	6
		Project Manager from UNIC European University Alliance	1
Research and Technology Organisation	1	Public Engagement Officer at Marei Research Institute	1
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental	1	Head of Engagement, Innovation for Societal	1

Institution or Innovation Agency		Impact, Irish Universities Association	
Civil Society Organisation	1	Housing Association Development	1
Industry			
Other			

10. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (max. 150 words)	<p>Enabling structured dialogue around the topic of Financial Sustainability in Research. Deepening mutual understanding across diverse perspectives around common issues and to shed light on how we might refine or devise interventions that can be advanced through CATALISI.</p> <p>Inviting a critical peer interrogation of UCC intervention area and activities, an anticipated outcome is the identification of potential follow up opportunities to enhance the effectiveness and impact-making efforts of local action plans and overall exploitation of CATALISI acceleration services (to present, seek feedback and enhance UCC's action plan for change).</p>
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (max. 500 words)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-explore the Policy Landscape and Context Conditions for Financial Sustainability for Research. For this purpose, the topic was explored from three levels of analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ European ▪ National (Irish) ▪ Local/Institutional (UCC) <p>The presenters: David O'Connell, Kate Morris and Martin Galvin/David Hogan highlighted the three layers of analysis of the topic by bringing the participant's attention to the issues and barriers affecting the European and Irish university environment and then focusing on UCC's specific difficulties and how the European/Irish national</p>

	<p>context affects the institution's capacity to seek funding and conduct research. Following the presentations, the participants had the opportunity to delve further into the topic by sharing experiences in their own national and institutional contexts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • David Hogan then introduced UCC's intervention areas and action plan, discussions of which were facilitated subsequently by Martin Galvin in which UCC sought feedback from the external participants for future implementation. • Finally, the event closed with a Co-Creation session with an initial ideation phase followed by a discussion of the topics of the presentations.
<p>Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (max. 500 words)</p>	<p>The primary challenges faced by UCC when it comes to research financing are connected to the substantial mismatch between what is asked from the Irish university ecosystem and what support it receives in monetary terms. As of September 2024, Irish universities have been underfunded, on average, to the tune of €304 million a year with over half of the research equipment in the country being over a decade old.</p> <p>While Ireland has a long-standing ambition to achieve a 2.5% of GNP in respect of Gross Expenditure on Research and Development (GERD), it has consistently fallen short of this target. The Programme for Research in Third-Level Institutions (PRTLTI) was an Irish Government programme that provided integrated financial support for research infrastructure. The last PRTLTI call was 15 years ago. A high proportion of total research income to the institution comes from a small number of large-scale research centres, such as the Tyndall National Institute. There is an institutional need to examine the financial health and sustainability of Investigator Led funding models.</p> <p>One risk of the current funding model is an over-focus on external funders, and consequently research priorities set by funding agencies. There is a narrowing of research topics with greater diversity needed, but also a curtailing of researcher in institutionally determined topics. There is an over-reliance on Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) funding, which is a potential risk to longer term financial sustainability.</p> <p>The current overhead model at UCC requires review and revision. Research income for the most part, solely covers direct project costs. In many cases, the small institutional</p>

	<p>overhead provided (indirect costs) by a grant does not sufficiently support the full cost to the institution of supporting a research grant. For example, grants require support from staff in the research office, finance office, legal office, human resources department, Library, and many other support services over the lifetime of the grant. Currently, indirect costs are distributed to the unit involved in the grant, with the University retaining a small percentage. There is no mechanism currently for retaining overhead institutionally to invest in strategic initiatives or capacity building initiatives.</p> <p>Increasingly UCC, as a local regional institution, is experiencing issues related to brain drain, talent retention and attraction.</p>
<p>Activities performed (Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following the presentation phase which focused on the challenges faced by the European, Irish and UCC contexts in research financing, the participants were asked to conduct a silent ideation activity focusing on the central topics of the presentations and framing them in their own national/institutional contexts and then write their findings on notes which mirrored a Miro board template to guide the discussion. It quickly became clear that the posed questions and topics on the Miro board were not necessary as the conversations evolved organically and transitioned between talking points seamlessly and without the need of a guiding structure to conduct the conversations. • Co-creation workshop dedicated to exploring new insights for transformation - to inform pathways for the implementation of institutional changes. The session introduced and invited critical peer interrogation of UCC intervention area and activities, through this dialogue, we critically examined and co-developed mutual learning around financial systems, models and mechanisms for enabling a financially sustainable research system that supports rich and diverse research community and activity at all levels.

11. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
 fairly successful
 not too successful

not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

The MML, followed by the co-creation workshop session, was attended by a manageable and close-knit group which allowed easy communication and interaction. The discussion demonstrated a high level of engagement with participants voluntarily sharing their opinions and perspectives. The flow of the exchanges demonstrated a deep understanding between the participants which manifested itself in the capacity of the group to seamlessly transition from one step of the MML to the next without feeling constrained by the event timeline. The group was able to easily explore the different topics at the centre of the event. New and insightful knowledge was effectively transferred between participants.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

The post-event survey demonstrated a general appreciation by part of the participants of the methods of engagement, the topics and then the insight UCC could give from its own local/institutional experience. When asked to rate from 1 to 5 (with 5 being a high level of satisfaction) the aspects of the event such as: the clarity of the event, its methodology, timing, available equipment and material provided, rhythm, structure and interaction; the survey responders all answered with votes between 4 and 5, indicating a high level of success.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (*max. 500 words*)

The methodology was very useful in fostering cooperation between the participants. The initial presentation conducted by a diverse and insightful selection of presenters showcased the topic of financial sustainability from a European, National Irish and Local Cork perspective and set the scene for the subsequent discussions between the participants which touched upon many key areas surrounding the topic.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (*max. 300 words*)

- UCC identified specific actions to follow up in relation to funding models in Netherlands, Lithuania, Spain as well as the potential specific income stream not previously considered.
- The discussions also highlighted the potential for collection of examples of models and mechanisms to support financial sustainability of research.
- Finally, key Insights were identified on diverse contexts around attracting and retaining research talent as well as on diverse policy contexts relevant to financial sustainability of research.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer.
(max. 150 words)

The conversations had during the event and the findings which resulted were further researched and integrated in the UCC Action Plans which were presented the subsequent week during the consortium meetings and other activities conducted with other parties from the initiative. Furthermore, a shared MML Doc will be compiled for the Participants to support follow up opportunities.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

The involvement of top-level managers, such as David O'Connell (Director of Research Support and Policy) who is also a PI on the project helps platform the project and institutional change within the university. Also, David Hogan's involvement in Catalisi and work on strategic planning for UCC is beneficial to the acceleration of change. Lessons from the MML can be formally fed back to the senior leadership team via the OVPRI and the Director of Strategic Planning and Research.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

Further integration of lessons learned during event in institution's action plans, exploration of new financing pathways identified thanks to the mutual learning session in the event (UCC will present a revised Action Plan to all stakeholders on Catalisi). Preparation of documentation for other participants to learn from UCC experiences both in relation to the topics analysed in the event as well as the preparatory aspects of the event. Exploration of new income streams.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

This is not the first time for the UCC representatives of using the co-creation workshop methodologies displayed during the MML for similar events and UCC will continue to exploit its advantages for future activities with CATALISI and beyond.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

The only noticeable complication regarding the event was the difficulty which some participants had in reaching the city to participate in person. Unfortunately, this is an issue which regards not only this CATALISI-related event but any such endeavour in cities which lack adequate transportation, and which is mostly beyond the control of the institution. That said, if this is an issue which might affect other institutions, the preparation of adequate online-based meeting functionalities can somewhat solve these issues.

12. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

KTU MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	Participatory Research Practices at KTU: Infrastructure and Strategic Guideline
Date	10-12-2024
Venue	Kaunas, KTU
Length	1 day
Total number of participants	14

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: [Kaunas University of Technology]

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. *This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.*

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	14	University level manager	1
		Faculty level manager	3
		Administrative staff	2
		Researchers	8
Research and Technology Organisation			0
			0
			0
Cluster or Business Organisation			0
			0
			0
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency			0
			0
			0
Civil Society Organisation			0
			0
			0

			0
Industry			0
			0
			0
Other			0
			0
			0

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)	The event aimed to discuss infrastructure, strategic guidelines, and real-world applications of citizen science projects across different fields.
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	<p>Addressing the agenda of the event, topics of the MML event were focussed on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introducing Citizen Science Guidelines at KTU: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presentation of the official guidelines for implementing citizen science projects at KTU. This provides the foundation for understanding how the university plans to engage the public in scientific research. The focus is on setting standards for quality, ethics, and collaboration in citizen science. 2. Activities of Citizen Science Hub: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - introduction the hub's role at KTU. This includes explaining the structure and goals of the hub, how it serves as a center for coordinating citizen science projects, and its role in fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The hub acts as a resource for students, researchers, and the general public interested in participating in or organizing citizen science initiatives. 3. Practices from Social Citizen Science Projects (TIME4CS, YouCount, LibOCS): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experiences of specific citizen science projects that focus on social issues. The projects mentioned— TIME4CS, YouCount, and LibOCS— acts as case studies illustrating how citizen science can address pressing social challenges and how citizen science activities might be fostered at the universities and libraries.

	<p>4. Citizen Science Projects in Architecture and Other Disciplines</p> <p>- discussion on how citizen science is being applied in architecture and possibly other fields, highlighting innovative approaches where the public helps gather data, provide insights, or even co-create solutions. These projects explore urban planning and environmental design.</p>
<p>Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas <i>(max. 500 words)</i></p>	<p>The main challenge/question, that was discussed at the MML event: How to enhance public engagement and inclusion of stakeholders, to solve societal challenges? Our long-term vision is to be a university implementing social change and cooperating with society. The medium-long goal is by the end of the project to achieve the increase in awareness of the university academic and research staff of the benefits of public engagement in research. Short-term goal is to enact citizen science hub.</p>
<p>Activities performed <i>(Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</i></p>	<p>Co-creation session was organized after the presentations. It was organized as an interactive discussion session (as World Cafe) and enabled attendees to ask questions, provide feedback, and share their experiences. The co-creation session covered all 3 intervention areas at KTU.</p>

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer *(max. 150 words)*.

The event was very successful. For KTU, a key measure of success is whether the insights or approaches discussed in the workshop led to actual changes in institutional practices. We received feedback from KTU colleagues indicating the possibilities of positive evaluation of transformations that are planned under the CATALISI project. This event helped sharing the experiences with partners and receive their feedback. This potentially will also foster future collaboration and drive collective growth.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

Will be filled in after the analysis of feedback survey data

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (max. 500 words)

Mutual Learning (MML) workshop methodology was very useful in fostering cooperation between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The MML workshop methodology is typically designed to promote active dialogue and sharing of best practices among HEIs. The workshop effectively facilitated open discussions, participants could share insights, experiences, and challenges related to the topics they were focusing on. MML workshops helped to build networks and relationships between institutions that can support future cooperation. It created an environment where HEIs can explore potential partnerships, develop new research projects, or other forms of collaboration.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

MML workshop helped to foster knowledge exchange, facilitate collaboration and networking, encourage joint problem-solving, which is aligned with institutional goals and can lead to changes in institutional practices.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

The insights gathered during the event will be used to refine strategies and enhance transformations of all 3 intervention areas. By analysing the feedback and key takeaways, we can identify areas for improvement and optimize our processes. The information will also help in better understanding emerging challenges.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

The event served as a catalyst for ideation on deeper engagement with educational opportunities (like Erasmus mobility), skill development (via writing clinics), and democratic participation in academic discourse (through citizen involvement in research). It not only advances specific pathways but also contributes to creating an interconnected educational ecosystem where mobility, learning, and collaboration are supported across multiple levels.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

In this MML we had middle level managers. We agree that having top-level managers would have accelerated the transformations. We will inform top-level managers about the outcomes of MML.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

The follow-up to this event is crucial for ensuring that the momentum built during the event is sustained and that the goals of enhancing Erasmus mobility, creating writing clinics, and fostering public participation in research are fully realized. We are thinking of the mentorship program, where former Erasmus teachers will mentor first-time participants, providing personalized advice on adjusting to new cultures. Also, we plan to develop a newsletter (blog) that highlights success stories. Also, we plan to test idea of writing clinic by organizing small peer-writing groups where participants can exchange drafts, give feedback, and discuss writing challenges.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

Yes, it was the first time when we organized MML. We think we will use this methodology even beyond the CATALISI project.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

N/A

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

AUTH MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	Integrating Open Citizen Science in Universities: Building Stakeholder Engagement and Living Lab Ecosystems
Date	22/01/2025
Venue	Aristotle University Research Dissemination Center (KEDEA)
Length	6:30 hours
Total number of participants	25

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. *This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.*

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	16	Research Associates	6
		PhD Candidates	3
		Professors	7
		Administrative	1
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency	6	Coordinator of Hellenic Academic Libraries Link	1
		Administrative Positions	2
		Project Manager	3
Industry	2	Communication Manager	1

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)	The CATALISI MML event aimed to bring together academic, professional, and community stakeholders to explore how Open Science and Citizen Science principles can be effectively integrated into higher education institutions. Through presentations, open discussions, and hands-on co-creation activities, the event supported mutual learning and the development of strategies for institutional
---	--

	<p>transformation at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. The gathering contributed to the broader goals of the Horizon Europe-funded CATALISI project, emphasizing stakeholder engagement, transparency, and societal impact through Living Labs and citizen-driven initiatives.</p>
<p>Summary of the main topic(s) covered (max. 500 words)</p>	<p>The central theme of the event was "Integrating Open Citizen Science in Universities: Building Stakeholder Engagement and Living Lab Ecosystems." The day-long event started with a guided tour of AUTH's library, offering insights into academic infrastructure that supports open access and knowledge sharing.</p> <p>The formal sessions began with an introduction to the CATALISI project and AUTH's strategic journey toward embedding Open Science principles. Speakers from AUTH and other Greek academic institutions presented on the current challenges and future opportunities for incorporating Open and Citizen Science within university systems.</p> <p>A major focus was on institutional structures that enable openness, collaboration, and broader engagement with society. Examples included contributions from the Hellenic Open Science Initiative and integration efforts from Greek universities. Topics included: improving transparency in research, managing open-access repositories, and using digital tools to support collaborative innovation.</p> <p>In the afternoon, a co-creation workshop encouraged participants to break into groups and explore actionable strategies to integrate Open and Citizen Science into AUTH's ecosystem. They worked on real-world challenges, particularly around data management, community collaboration, and policy development. The outcomes of this workshop are expected to shape AUTH's forthcoming action plan.</p> <p>The final session featured a showcase by Thess-AHALL, the university's Living Lab, demonstrating how researchers and community members can collaborate in real-world settings to address health challenges through co-creation processes.</p>
<p>Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (max. 500 words)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional Resistance to Change: Like many HEIs, AUTH is navigating entrenched structures and practices that make the integration of open science principles complex. The event facilitated dialogue around these barriers and strategies for cultural transformation. • Stakeholder Engagement: AUTH has made strides in involving external communities (e.g., through Thess-AHALL), but sustaining long-

	<p>term engagement remains a challenge. The co-creation session helped explore models for deeper, bidirectional collaboration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Structured Frameworks: There is a need for clearer, more systematic frameworks for managing and sharing data across departments. This includes ensuring FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data practices and harmonized policies. • Awareness and Capacity Building: Not all staff and researchers are familiar with Open Science or Citizen Science approaches. The event served as a platform for capacity building and peer learning, especially through practical examples and the Thess-AHALL showcase.
<p>Activities performed <i>(Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided Tour: Participants began the day with a tour of AUTH's library, focusing on its role in supporting Open Science infrastructures and academic access. • Open Discussion & Q&A: After the morning presentations, an open discussion session encouraged participants to ask questions and share perspectives on barriers to Open Science implementation. • Co-creation Workshop: The core interactive session involved small-group activities where stakeholders identified institutional challenges and proposed concrete solutions. Each group addressed themes such as integrating citizen input into research, improving data governance, and embedding openness into teaching and research practices. • Living Lab Showcase: Thess-AHALL demonstrated how real-world health challenges are tackled through collaborative Living Lab methods. This session highlighted best practices and successful engagement with citizens, clinicians, and researchers.

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
 fairly successful
 not too successful
 not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (max. 150 words).

The event was **fairly successful**, achieving its main goal of initiating dialogue and collaborative thinking around Open and Citizen Science integration at AUTH. While many participants were from existing project partners, it still offered valuable exchanges. Particularly, the involvement of administrative and governmental representatives from the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link provided insightful feedback that underlined the importance of institutional transformation and Open Science as a national priority. However, a broader participation across faculties and external stakeholders would have further enriched the outcomes, which slightly limited the event's full potential.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

Participants rated the event positively overall. Feedback highlighted the relevance of the thematic focus—particularly the integration of Open Science, Citizen Science, and institutional transformation in higher education. The co-creation session stood out as a meaningful opportunity for active dialogue and collaboration, encouraging participants to share practical ideas and reflect on institutional challenges. The participation of experts from the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link (HEAL-Link) was seen as particularly valuable, as their insights added a national perspective on Open Access policy and FAIR data practices. Some participants suggested future events could benefit from increased representation across disciplines, student voices, and civil society actors.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (max. 500 words)

The MML workshop methodology proved effective in fostering a productive mutual learning process. The format, which combined presentations, discussions, and hands-on co-creation activities, encouraged a participatory approach and allowed participants to share knowledge and insights from their own experiences. This collaborative environment was key to promoting the exchange of ideas about Open Science and Citizen Science integration in universities.

Through the co-creation session, participants were able to work together to identify challenges and propose concrete solutions, creating a shared sense of ownership over the transformation process. The collaborative nature of the event allowed for a variety of perspectives from both academia and external stakeholders to come together, enriching the conversation with different insights. The participation of stakeholders such as those from the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link brought a national level perspective, which highlighted broader trends and challenges related to Open Science policies and practices.

Additionally, the diversity of stakeholders—from university administrators to policy makers—helped to build a common understanding of the issues at hand, which is critical in fostering cooperation between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). While not all faculties were represented, the involvement of administrative and governmental representatives provided an opportunity to break down silos and align strategic goals across different institutions and sectors. This helped reinforce the importance of collective action in driving Open Science integration across the HEIs involved.

In conclusion, the methodology helped to strengthen collaboration among HEIs by facilitating joint problem-solving, aligning institutional strategies, and providing practical

solutions to complex issues. By bringing together different sectors and stakeholders, it promoted a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to integrating Open and Citizen Science in academic settings.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

The biggest takeaway from the MML event was the importance of creating structures within universities that truly support openness and collaboration. We learned how essential it is to build a culture that embraces Open Science and Citizen Science, not just as theoretical concepts, but as practical approaches to research and education.

The co-creation workshop was particularly valuable in highlighting the real barriers that exist in integrating these practices, like institutional resistance to change and the lack of clear frameworks for data management. But it also showed us that with the right strategies, these challenges can be overcome. We also learned how important it is to involve stakeholders early on and make them active participants in the transformation process, as this can lead to more sustainable change.

Another key lesson was the need for continuous capacity building. While we made great strides, not everyone at AUTH is yet familiar with Open Science, so there's still a lot of work to do in terms of training and awareness-raising.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

The insights from the event will be used to shape AUTH's action plan for integrating Open Science and Citizen Science. The co-creation session provided concrete ideas that will be built into our strategies for tackling data governance, stakeholder engagement, and fostering collaboration across departments. The feedback on institutional barriers will also be useful as we work to address resistance to change and create a more open culture at the university. We'll focus on engaging stakeholders early and setting up frameworks that encourage openness and accessibility, particularly in terms of data sharing and academic collaboration.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

The event was an important step in advancing our transformational pathway because it allowed us to confront some of the institutional barriers we're facing head-on. The discussions around resistance to change, the need for structured frameworks, and stakeholder engagement were timely and relevant. It gave us the tools and ideas to address these challenges more effectively.

By showcasing the Thess-AHALL Living Lab's success in involving citizens in health research, the event also gave us a model to follow in terms of practical application. The interactive workshops helped us come up with actionable steps that can be implemented within AUTH, helping to create the environment necessary for Open and Citizen Science practices to thrive.

The event also allowed us to identify gaps in our current processes, like the lack of clarity around data management practices, which is a key focus for our next steps.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (*if any*) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

Involving top-level managers such as Mr. Panagiotis Bamidis, Director of the Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Laboratory, and Mrs. Lia Ollandezou, Coordinator of HEAL-Link, played a key role in accelerating the transformation process. Having decision-makers like them present allowed for a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities that Open Science and Citizen Science present. Their involvement not only brought valuable insights but also gave them the platform to champion the necessary changes within the institution, ensuring that the required resources are allocated for successful implementation.

One of the key takeaways from the event was the recognition that transformation needs strong leadership—both from researchers and administrators. Top-level managers are essential in driving the cultural shift towards openness and collaboration. Their participation in the event highlighted the critical role they play in fostering this change at the university level, emphasizing the need for strategic leadership in driving forward the institutional transformation.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

The follow-up of the event will focus on incorporating the ideas and strategies discussed into AUTH's action plan for Open Science and Citizen Science. This will include concrete steps to improve stakeholder engagement, build capacity, and develop clearer frameworks for data management.

The outcomes of the co-creation workshop will be used to guide the development of these strategies, ensuring they are practical and actionable. In addition, further discussions with both internal and external stakeholders will be organized to continue the conversation around integration and sustainability.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

While this is our first time explicitly using the MML (Mutual Learning) methodology in this formal format, we have long been working with similar participatory approaches, particularly in co-creation workshops and stakeholder engagement activities. Although we didn't call them "MML," the core principles of fostering collaboration, knowledge sharing, and collective problem-solving have been integral to our work.

Moving forward, we absolutely plan to adopt and replicate this methodology for other topics, particularly those requiring cultural shifts or collaborative innovation, such as research integrity, sustainability, and digital transformation. The participatory, inclusive nature of MML allows us to tap into diverse perspectives, ensuring more comprehensive and effective solutions. However, challenges like aligning the schedules and priorities of all relevant stakeholders—often influenced by personal interests, time constraints, and even financial or grant limitations—mean that while the methodology is valuable, its implementation will need careful timing and planning.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

Based on the feedback, it would be beneficial to increase the representation of diverse disciplines and external stakeholders in future events. Involving more students, civil society actors, and researchers from different fields would provide a broader range of perspectives and ideas.

Additionally, future MMLs could include more interactive, hands-on activities that allow participants to prototype solutions to real-world challenges. This would help maintain engagement and ensure that participants leave with concrete, actionable ideas they can implement at their own institutions.

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

UG MML WORKSHOP REPORT

1. General Information

Event Title	MML Workshop at UG: Social engagement in Higher Education. Building stakeholders cooperations and reaching out to external partners
Date	11.04.2025
Venue	Faculty of Economics, University of Gdańsk, ul. Armii Krajowej 119/121, 81-824 Sopot
Length	8.55-15.30
Total number of participants	9 onsite, 6 online, plus 3 experts in the workshop, altogether 18

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: [University of Gdańsk]

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. *This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.*

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia	14	Vice-dean	1
		Administrative staff (Rectors office)	1
		Researchers	12
Research and Technology Organisation			
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency			

Civil Society Organisation	1	APRE	1
Industry	3	Manager in a big company	3
Other			

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (max. 150 words)	The aim of the CATALISI Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) event at the University of Gdańsk was to strengthen societal engagement in higher education by fostering collaboration between universities and external stakeholders. As part of the Horizon Europe CATALISI project, the event focused on sharing best practices, identifying barriers, and co-developing solutions for engaging with businesses, schools, NGOs, and public institutions. Through workshops, participatory observation, and interactive discussions, participants explored how universities can effectively implement their “third mission” of societal contribution beyond traditional teaching and research. The event also aimed to enhance knowledge transfer, support institutional transformation, and build sustainable stakeholder cooperation.
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (max. 500 words)	<p>The event explored the university's “third mission”—its role in contributing to society through outreach, knowledge exchange, and collaboration with non-academic partners. Special emphasis was placed on understanding how to engage with various stakeholders, including secondary schools, businesses, NGOs, and public agencies. Participants examined practical ways to sustain long-term partnerships and identified the key benefits of such collaborations for both universities and their external partners.</p> <p>One of the central topics was the presentation of best practices from the University of Gdańsk,</p>

particularly its involvement in educational outreach initiatives such as the **Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad**—a national competition for high school students. This served as a real-time case study of a large-scale event involving more than a hundred external stakeholders. MML participants had the opportunity to engage in **participatory observation**, attending Olympiad sessions and accompanying workshops, which gave firsthand insight into how external engagement can be successfully organized and implemented.

The event included a two-part **co-creation workshop** designed to foster collaborative problem-solving. In the first session, participants identified key **barriers** to stakeholder engagement, such as administrative constraints, differing expectations, lack of incentives, or limited communication. In the second part, they proposed **solutions and tools** to overcome these obstacles—ranging from improved partnership models and joint initiatives to targeted communication strategies and supportive institutional policies.

Another important topic was the **role of business partners** in advancing societal engagement. A dedicated session explored how universities can develop and maintain ties with the private sector to support academic activities, foster innovation, and contribute to regional development. This discussion highlighted the need for **mutual understanding, transparency, and shared value creation** between academia and industry.

Throughout the event, participants addressed critical questions including:

- What are the most effective models of societal engagement?
- Which actors should be prioritized for collaboration?
- How can knowledge be shared outside traditional academic settings?
- How do universities balance academic missions with societal expectations?

By the end of the event, a draft list of challenges and actionable solutions was developed, laying the groundwork for ongoing collaboration among CATALISI project partners and beyond. The insights and outcomes of this MML event are expected to contribute significantly to institutional transformation

	<p>processes within HEIs and help shape future engagement strategies.</p>
<p>Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas <i>(max. 500 words)</i></p>	<p>The Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) event at the University of Gdańsk addressed several core institutional challenges related to societal engagement, which align with key intervention areas identified in the CATALISI project, particularly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Societal Engagement and Third Mission • Stakeholder Involvement and Collaboration • Knowledge Transfer and Exchange • Institutional Transformation and Capacity Building <p>1. Lack of Systematic Stakeholder Engagement Strategy</p> <p>One of the central challenges is the absence of a cohesive, long-term strategy for engaging with a diverse range of external stakeholders. Engagement often depends on individual staff initiatives rather than structured institutional planning. During the event, this was discussed as a barrier to achieving continuity and scalability in collaboration with businesses, schools, NGOs, and government agencies.</p> <p>2. Third Mission Not Fully Integrated into Institutional Identity</p> <p>While the university actively undertakes outreach initiatives, such as the Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad, the "third mission" is still not fully embedded in the university's strategic vision and everyday operations. Participants noted the need to institutionalize societal engagement and ensure it is valued equally with teaching and research.</p> <p>3. Challenges in Knowledge Transfer Beyond Academia</p> <p>Another significant challenge is effectively translating academic knowledge into practical applications that benefit non-academic audiences. The event explored how HEIs can develop more inclusive communication strategies and partnership models to reach target groups that typically fall outside traditional academic settings, such as SMEs, local government bodies, or underrepresented communities.</p> <p>4. Administrative and Structural Barriers</p> <p>Participants identified internal constraints such as rigid organizational procedures, limited incentives, and insufficient support structures for staff working</p>

	<p>on external engagement. These issues hinder flexibility and discourage experimentation in developing new forms of collaboration with external stakeholders.</p> <p>5. Uneven Business Collaboration</p> <p>Although there are successful examples of university-business cooperation, including joint educational events and research projects, the level of engagement remains inconsistent across faculties and disciplines. Challenges include differences in communication styles, lack of shared objectives, and unclear mechanisms for partnership development.</p> <p>6. Fragmented Data on Engagement Activities</p> <p>A cross-cutting issue discussed was the lack of centralized data collection on stakeholder involvement and outreach activities. Without clear tracking and evaluation mechanisms, it is difficult to measure impact, identify gaps, or replicate successful initiatives.</p> <p>7. Limited Student Involvement in Third Mission Activities</p> <p>The event also highlighted that students are often passive participants in outreach activities. One of the challenges identified is finding ways to involve students more meaningfully—as co-creators and ambassadors of societal engagement—thus enriching their learning experience and boosting civic responsibility.</p> <p>The MML event provided a platform to surface these challenges and start developing concrete, collaborative solutions. Addressing them will support the University of Gdańsk's broader transformation under the CATALISI framework and enhance its role as a socially engaged institution.</p>
<p>Activities performed <i>(Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words)</i></p>	<p>The MML event at the University of Gdańsk on April 11, 2025, was highly interactive and structured around a mix of presentations, participatory observation, group discussions, and collaborative workshops designed to engage participants in a hands-on exploration of societal engagement practices.</p> <hr/> <p>1. Opening Presentations and Case Studies</p> <p>The event began with introductory presentations on the CATALISI project and the concept of societal</p>

	<p>engagement in higher education, followed by a session showcasing UG's practices. Key examples included collaborations with local schools, business entities, and non-academic partners. A case study on the Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad highlighted how the university organized a national-scale outreach event involving over a hundred external stakeholders. This set the stage for practical reflection on the challenges and enablers of such initiatives.</p> <hr/> <p>2. Participatory Observation</p> <p>Participants took part in a field visit to the Olympiad, which was taking place concurrently. This "live" participatory observation allowed them to witness several event components, including student competitions, teacher workshops, and laboratory demonstrations. Participants had the opportunity to interact with organizers and participants, observe the organizational setup, and reflect on real-time examples of university-society collaboration in action.</p> <hr/> <p>3. Co-Creation Workshop – Part 1: Identifying Barriers</p> <p>A key interactive activity was the co-creation workshop, where participants were divided into subgroups based on different types of stakeholders (e.g. businesses, schools, NGOs, public authorities). Each group discussed and identified barriers to effective stakeholder engagement from their institutional perspectives. Issues raised included lack of clear communication channels, low stakeholder involvement in strategic planning, and insufficient institutional incentives for staff engagement efforts.</p> <hr/> <p>4. Business Engagement Session</p> <p>A targeted discussion on engaging with business stakeholders featured presentations by Dariusz Tłoczyński and invited business representatives. This session examined how HEIs can build and sustain partnerships with the private sector and how business actors perceive their roles in supporting academic institutions beyond funding, such as co-creating educational content or participating in skill-building programs.</p>
--	--

	<p>5. Co-Creation Workshop – Part 2: Developing Solutions</p> <p>In the afternoon, the co-creation workshop resumed with a focus on generating solutions to the barriers previously identified. Groups proposed tools and strategies such as structured stakeholder mapping, shared governance models, dedicated engagement coordinators, and incentive systems to encourage staff and student involvement. These outputs were collected for further development after the event.</p> <hr/> <p>4.2.3.1. 6. Networking Opportunities</p> <p>In addition to structured activities, the event included informal networking sessions, such as coffee breaks and a lunch gathering, which facilitated further exchange of experiences and ideas. The day concluded with a dinner at Olivia Star, offering participants an informal setting to continue discussions and strengthen connections.</p> <p>These practical and collaborative activities not only encouraged the exchange of knowledge but also laid the foundation for concrete follow-up steps in enhancing societal engagement strategies within the CATALISI framework.</p>
--	---

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

The MML event at the University of Gdańsk was highly successful in fostering meaningful dialogue and collaboration around societal engagement in higher education. Participants actively engaged in workshops, discussions, and live observation of the Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad, gaining valuable insights into real-life stakeholder involvement. The co-creation sessions led to the identification of key challenges and the development of practical, actionable solutions tailored to various stakeholder groups. The event facilitated strong networking among academics, business representatives, and public sector actors, creating momentum for future collaborations. Feedback from participants

highlighted the relevance of the topics, the usefulness of the participatory format, and the event's well-balanced combination of theory and practice. Importantly, it contributed directly to the CATALISI project's goal of institutional transformation, providing both the University of Gdańsk and other HEIs with tools and ideas to strengthen their third mission and societal impact.

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

Based on the feedback survey, participants rated the MML event at the University of Gdańsk very highly. The average score across key areas was between **4.0 and 4.67 out of 5**, indicating a strong level of satisfaction. Attendees especially appreciated the **high level of interaction and participation (4.67)**, the **collaborative nature of the activities (4.67)**, and the opportunity to share insights freely (4.67). The event was also seen as effective in **broadening perspectives (4.67)** and **meeting participants' expectations (4.67)**. While the generation of new ideas received a slightly lower but still positive rating (4.00), overall feedback reflects that the workshop format was **engaging, relevant, and well-structured**. Most participants expressed interest in future events and considered the workshop model **replicable within their own institutions**.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (max. 500 words)

The MML workshop methodology proved to be an effective and engaging approach for supporting **mutual learning and cooperation between HEIs**, particularly in the context of societal engagement and stakeholder collaboration. By combining presentations, participatory observation, and co-creation workshops, the methodology created an inclusive environment that encouraged both knowledge sharing and joint problem-solving.

The design of the MML allowed participants not only to learn from institutional best practices but also to engage with real-world examples. The **participatory observation** of the Logistics and Forwarding Olympiad offered a unique opportunity to experience first-hand how the University of Gdańsk interacts with external stakeholders—in this case, secondary schools and teachers. This dynamic, on-the-ground exposure made abstract ideas about engagement more tangible and transferable.

The **co-creation workshops**, divided into two parts, were particularly successful in activating collaboration. In Part 1, groups identified shared **challenges** in engaging with businesses, NGOs, schools, and public bodies. In Part 2, they worked collaboratively to develop **practical solutions** and tools. This format ensured that discussions were grounded in participants' real institutional experiences and that outputs were relevant and actionable.

One of the key strengths of the MML methodology is that it encourages **horizontal knowledge exchange** rather than a top-down transfer of information. Participants from different HEIs had the opportunity to voice their insights, reflect on local contexts, and

learn from one another's successes and obstacles. The high levels of interaction and openness fostered **trust and peer learning**, which are crucial for long-term cooperation.

In terms of addressing the chosen topic—**societal engagement in HEIs**—the methodology was particularly well-suited. By centering the discussions on concrete stakeholder groups and involving real events (like the Olympiad), the MML created a strong link between theory and practice. It allowed HEIs to explore how societal engagement can be structurally embedded into their missions and how cooperation with external actors can be expanded.

In conclusion, the MML methodology significantly contributed to the mutual learning process and fostered **cross-institutional dialogue and cooperation**.

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

One of the most valuable components was the **workshop with business stakeholders**, which offered practical insights into building and maintaining effective university-business partnerships. Participants emphasized the importance of aligning academic goals with business needs and fostering long-term, trust-based collaboration. The session also highlighted that businesses are willing to support universities not only through funding but also by **co-developing programs, providing mentorship, and engaging in joint projects**, particularly those with societal impact. This workshop was widely regarded as a highlight of the event for its relevance, depth, and transferability to participants' home institutions.

Another major achievement was the **identification of key barriers and enablers** of stakeholder cooperation through co-creation workshops. These discussions helped clarify institutional gaps, such as fragmented engagement strategies and limited incentive systems, while generating actionable ideas like stakeholder mapping, cross-sector platforms, and internal engagement support roles.

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

The insights gained during the MML event will be used to enhance the University of Gdańsk's institutional strategy for societal engagement by integrating more structured and sustainable collaboration models with external stakeholders. Key takeaways—particularly from the business stakeholder workshop—will inform the development of clearer partnership frameworks and more targeted communication strategies with industry partners. The identified barriers and proposed solutions from the co-creation sessions will support internal policy adjustments, including improved coordination across faculties and better support for staff engaged in third mission activities. The event also highlighted the value of cross-sector dialogue, which will inspire the creation of new spaces for regular exchange between the university and external actors.

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

First, the event provided a structured opportunity to **critically reflect on current engagement practices** and identify gaps that limit the university's third mission effectiveness. Through collaborative workshops, participants mapped out specific barriers—such as fragmented strategies, limited incentives, and insufficient communication with stakeholders—and proposed realistic, context-sensitive solutions. These outputs will directly feed into the refinement of our institutional action plan.

Second, the **session with business stakeholders** proved to be especially valuable, offering insight into how universities can build meaningful, long-term partnerships with industry. This aligns directly with our transformation goals of increasing external impact and co-developing solutions to real-world challenges. The shared experiences and success factors presented by business representatives will inform a more strategic, partnership-oriented approach within our pathway.

Additionally, the **participatory observation of the Olympiad** reinforced the importance of designing engagement activities that are both large in scale and deeply rooted in academic goals. It showcased how societal engagement can be integrated into core educational missions, helping us envision new, scalable models of outreach.

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

Definitely yes—the involvement of top-level managers in the MML event significantly contributes to accelerating institutional transformation in the areas discussed, particularly societal engagement and stakeholder cooperation.

The active participation of leadership—such as Vice-Dean **Magdalena Markiewicz**, who opened the event and contributed to key discussions—ensured that the topics addressed were not only acknowledged but also **strategically prioritized** within the university's broader development goals. Their presence stressed a strong institutional commitment to advancing the third mission and created a sense of ownership and legitimacy around the outcomes of the MML.

Top-level managers are in a unique position to **translate workshop insights into action** by aligning them with institutional policies, allocating resources, and integrating new practices into formal strategies. Their involvement helps bridge the gap between bottom-up ideas and top-down decision-making, ensuring that innovative approaches—such as improved stakeholder collaboration models or incentives for societal engagement—are not lost at the implementation stage.

Moreover, the presence of leadership encouraged open and solution-oriented dialogue among participants and sent a clear message to external stakeholders (e.g., business representatives) that the university values and supports long-term cooperation.

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

The follow-up to the MML event will focus on translating the insights and proposed solutions into concrete actions within the University of Gdańsk's institutional

transformation strategy (including action plan). The outcomes of the co-creation workshops, particularly the identified barriers and solutions for stakeholder engagement, will be reviewed and integrated into an updated action plan under the CATALISI project. A working group will be established to further develop the partnership models discussed, especially those involving businesses (also within living labs). Additionally, the university plans to document and share good practices from the Olympiad and the business engagement session with other HEIs in the CATALISI network. Participants who expressed interest will be invited to future MML workshops, and efforts will be made to sustain dialogue with external stakeholders engaged during the event. Overall, the event serves as a launchpad for long-term improvements in societal engagement and institutional collaboration.

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

Yes, this was our **first experience using the MML workshop methodology**, and it proved to be highly effective and adaptable. The combination of interactive workshops, real-life observation, and structured group collaboration created a dynamic learning environment that encouraged deep reflection, peer exchange, and actionable outcomes. It successfully engaged both internal and external stakeholders and enabled participants to co-develop practical solutions to real institutional challenges.

Given its success, we **definitely plan to replicate this format** for other strategic topics and initiatives beyond the CATALISI project—particularly in areas such as innovation ecosystems, sustainability in education, and digital transformation. The flexible structure of the MML format allows it to be tailored to various themes, while still promoting cross-sector dialogue and internal alignment. It also serves as a powerful tool for mobilizing diverse institutional actors, fostering ownership, and supporting evidence-based decision-making.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

As we are not so experienced, we do not have any suggestions. We collected the voices of the participants that we should avoid the activities (even if only observations) only in Polish.

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).

APPENDIX C – MML TOOLKIT

MML WORKSHOP ORGANISATION CHECKLIST

APRE as facilitator:

- Provides MML Kit (Agenda template, MML Final Report, MML Checklist)
- Organises regular meeting to guide the Implementers during the organisation on the MML
- Supports the Implementers in finding speakers (if needed) and in organising the whole process.
- Facilitates the workshop onsite

Implementer

Steps	Status (in Progress- completed)	Notes
Identify the Workshop Team		<i>Define people supporting in the organization and their roles and responsibilities</i>
Set date and time of the event		<i>Consider the availability of the target audience and convenience for the your organization</i>
Lists potential participants		<i>Evaluate the potential number of participants among internal and external stakeholders taking into account the topic discussed (e.g. researchers, civil society, public administration etc.)</i>
Seek and book proper venue		<i>Find the location and book well in advance according to the potential participants</i>
Define Workshop topic		<i>Clearly outline the purpose and expected outcomes of the workshop.</i>
Draft the Programme		<i>Design a detailed program with session topics, speakers, and time slots, interactive section. Use the Agenda MML template</i>
Recruit the speakers and facilitators		<i>Contact the speakers/ and facilitators needed according to number of participants and groups during co-creation session</i>

Set registration system		<i>It is useful to draft a registration form to track attendees (a. Name, b. Surname, c. Email, d. Organization, e. Type,) according to CATALISI GDPR rule set Privacy Policy</i>
Send early bird invitation		Send early invitation (e-mail, individual invitations) to save-the-date
Specify workshop set-up		Arrange logistics (e.g. chairs, tables needed)
Organise equipment		Ensure technical equipment (projectors, microphones) and have technical support available during the workshop.
Organise food and beverage according to budget available		Contact the catering, consider dietary restrictions and preferences of participants.
Send invitations		Send final Programme to participants
Send reminder		Closer to the workshop date and any necessary pre-workshop materials (if any).
Material preparation		Collect PPT presentations well in advance, and in case needed print final agenda, other working materials. Evaluate if needed post-it, pens and other whiteboards for co-creation session.
Organise the dissemination of the workshop		Plan how to disseminate Internal or via social media both of the projects and of the organization the event. Liaise with F6S for communication and dissemination guidelines.
Get feedback		Create a feedback survey for participants to get an assessment on the workshop.
Follow-up activities		Send materials shared during the events and outcomes to participants
Draft the MML Report		See appendix A of D2.1

AGENDA TEMPLATE WITH GUIDELINES

CATALISI MML EVENT [TITLE]

DRAFT AGENDA
[DATE, VENUE, TIME]

Organizer name, partner of the project CATALISI (<https://catalisi.eu/>) is organising this event [MML are events where Implementers can exchange experiences and knowledge on their respective intervention areas and transformational pathways] with the aim to [add short **concept note** of the event with clear definitions of expected outputs and outcomes*, topic** and participants, for example by using the format of the reporting template. You may also include the definition of guiding questions to instil interest in the topic].

***Outputs and outcomes:** it is important to define the intended output and outcome, otherwise it is challenging to have a focused and meaningful dialogue that actually sets change in motion. Outputs are defined as results achieved immediately after the event (e.g. documents, reports, etc.), while outcomes are defined as longer-term results, such as follow-up activities.

****Topic:** it is important to formulate a **clear topic** to define the problem that requires further understanding and to formulate potential solutions with the contribution of all event participants.

- To identify the topic, CATALISI partners should define the **intervention area** which is more relevant to share and to have inputs/feedback from the invited participants and stakeholders, and which could enable them to achieve institutional changes in the long-run.
- To identify the topic, CATALISI partners should define the **intervention area** which is more relevant to share and to have inputs/feedback from the invited participants and stakeholders, and which could enable them to achieve institutional changes in the long-run.

Add a brief abstract of the day, summarizing participants*** who will take part in the activities (be precise and define both the speakers and the participants that will be invited to event i.e. internal and external stakeholders and the and type of participants (e.g. Academia, Research Funding Organizations, Policy-Makers, Civil Society, Business, CS initiatives, others to specify).

*****Participants:** Depending on the overall aim of the event organized, select participants to invite to ensure the most productive environment. It is also important to keep in mind an appropriate number of participants. A large number of participants may not always be the right choice, especially for events where concrete actions have to be defined.

The following actors are highly encouraged to participate:

- **Different hierarchical levels inside the organization (low, middle and top-managers).** Involving **top-level managers** in MML workshops is key to achieve organizational change.
- **Participants beyond the project team (i.e. core and extended team)** to stimulate collaboration between different groups and departments, in accordance with the topic of interest which is discussed.

- **External actors from the quadruple-helix** to enable meaningful and useful exchange between the academia and outside realm. At the same time, it is important to keep a balanced representation across the participants (e.g. types of quadruple helix actors, gender, etc.), unless the specific topic of the event is clearly of more interest to a specific category of stakeholders.

Define the agenda and speakers according to the workshop set-up:

- Session 1**** devoted to a frontal open exchange on inspirational examples (e.g. roundtable).

******Session 1:** this part will present **Inspirational examples** that host implementer will share on the intervention areas and their ongoing processes of institutional transformation. This part will provide the opportunity to introduce and discuss the specificities of each selected intervention area, ongoing processes, and successful examples. It will also allow for the contribution of speakers/stakeholders from different parts of the host institution (including **low, middle and top-level managers of HEIs**) and from the **quadruple-helix**, providing potentially unique insights and first-hand experiences.

It is important to invite **experts for keynote speeches**. They can bring their expertise to the discussion as a showcase of success cases and stories, role models, the point of view of a High-Level Institution.

- Session 2***** co-creating new pathways for the implementations of institutional changes.

*******Session 2:** Implementers will have the opportunity to allow **exchange and discussion** with speakers and participants. In this part, co-creation session, specific methodologies will be adopted (flipcharts, billboard, post-its, interactive digital means etc.).

Depending on the state of implementation of transformational actions, this session may aim to:

- Provide implementers with input and solution of problems on their ongoing institutional transformation roadmap, discussing and evaluating, the transformational roadmaps with local actors and other participants.
- Discuss achievements, impacts and the sustainability of the implemented actions.
- Support the generation of new knowledge and ideas for all other participating HEIs in the specific area of intervention discussed.

Add link to registration form.

Agenda [example: indicative]

Start time	End time	Item description	Presenter
09:30	10:00	Welcome and Introduction to the project	Representative from host HEI Representative from APRE

10:00	11:30	Frontal session [TITLE]	Vice-rector External speaker CATALISI HEI
11:30	11:45	Q&A	
11:45	12:00	COFFEE BREAK	
12:00	14:00	Co-creation session* [TITLE AND DETAILS]	[APRE and CATALISI HEI as moderators]
14:00		LUNCH	
15:00		End of meeting	

***Co-creation session:** For co-creation activities during MML workshops, Implementers are encouraged to keep a balance between keeping the topic broad enough to benefit from the contribution of different actors, and at the same time narrow enough to ensure that the interaction leads to concrete outputs (e.g. actions to include in the Roadmaps). As participants are attending on a voluntary basis, it is crucial that the topic is relevant for them and that they see the importance of their contribution to the project's activities in a friendly and positive environment.

This part can be based on different formats, including brainstorming sessions, and guided discussions. Implementing partner countries can choose to adjust or even use different MML techniques if they believe that this is needed to achieve the desirable dialogue and outcome. For a list of techniques to use see section 6.6 of D2.1.

EXAMPLE OF EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE FOR EXTERNAL PARTICIPANTS

INSTRUCTIONS

- Please, consider that this is only an example of how you can structure a feedback survey for the participants to your MML. Feel free to adapt it.
- Please, put the survey in an *online* form. You can use the tool that you and/or your institution usually use (i.e. google form, Microsoft form, etc).
- Please, send this survey to participants no later than 1 week after the MML took place.
- You can ask to fill in the survey anonymously. You can choose the option you prefer (anonymously or not), however if you decide to submit it not anonymously, please remember to include GDPR reference according to UJI rules.
- The results of this survey will serve to your organization to evaluate the MML workshop and will be useful to develop the MML Report that you will submit to APRE and that will be used to develop the D2.2 – Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Report.

The example of evaluation questionnaire is available here:
<https://forms.office.com/e/8CaTTqGCc3>.

MML REPORT TEMPLATE

1. General Information

Event Title	
Date	
Venue	
Length	
Total number of participants	

2. Organizer information

Name of the organizer in charge of the event: [Insert Organization Name]

Person of reference: [Insert person's name and contact details]

3. Type of Participants

Please include how many participants for each type of organizations took part in the MML. *This information can be collected from the feedback survey sent to the MML participants. To fill in the table, refer to the example below.*

Type of organization	Number of participants	Role	N.
Academia			
Research and Technology Organisation			
Cluster or Business Organisation			
Policy Body, Governmental Institution or Innovation Agency			
Civil Society Organisation			

Industry			
Other			

4. Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event (<i>max. 150 words</i>)	
Summary of the main topic(s) covered (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	
Main challenges in your organization addressed during the event connected to the intervention areas (<i>max. 500 words</i>)	
Activities performed (<i>Briefly describe any practical activities and/or Group discussions or collaborative activities; max 500 words</i>)	

5. Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer (*max. 150 words*).

How did participants rate this event? Please, take into account the feedback surveys' answers by providing us with a brief overall analysis.

How do you evaluate the use of this methodology (MML workshop) in the mutual learning process? Did this methodology help to foster cooperation between HEIs with reference to the topics you have chosen for your MML? Please, justify your answer. (max. 500 words)

What were the most important achievements/learning outcomes/lessons learned of the MML event? (max. 300 words)

How will you use the insights received during the event? Please justify your answer. (max. 150 words)

How and in what way was the event useful for the advancement of your transformational pathway? Please justify your answer. (max. 300 words)

Do you think that the involvement of top-level managers (if any) in the event will contribute to accelerate the transformation in the areas discussed? (max. 300 words)

What will be the follow-up of this event? (max. 150 words)

Is this your first experience using this kind of methodology? Do you think you will replicate this format for other aims/topics in your institution beyond CATALISI project? Please, justify your answer.

Recommendations/suggestions for future MMLs based on your experience and on the results emerged from the feedback survey sent to participants (if any).

6. Follow-up materials

Please, upload the MML event materials on CATALISI SharePoint (i.e. Agenda, ppt presentations, Attendance list, photos, etc).